

SATISFACTORY

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Industrial lab use case Set-up and Demonstration

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AR	Augmented Reality
BSC	Business Scenario
CIDEM	Common Information Data Exchange Model
DM	Device Manager
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
HMI	Human Machine Interface
LM	Localization Manager
OM	Ontology Manager
PDEC	Plant Data Exchange Component
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UWB	Ultra Wide Band
VR	Virtual Reality
WO	Work Order
WP	Work Package
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP5. SatisFactory aims to develop an ecosystem of innovative technological components that would assist the daily operations of the people working at industrial environment. More specifically the developments of SatisFactory will be demonstrated to three diverse shop floors from discrete manufacturing (COMAU), batch products manufacturing (SUNLIGHT Systems) and continuous processes (CERTH/CPERI). The main focus of the project is around the workers and how to improve their daily activities and increase the collaboration and engagement to the shop floor operations. A user centred approach through an iterative development process with participation of the relevant stakeholders is applied to continuously guide and also validate project developments at the shop floors.

Deliverable D5.3 "Industrial lab use case Set-up and Demonstration" documents the overall context for the deployment of SatisFactory tools and components at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor to exemplify their usage at a pre-industrial level. The activities described in this deliverable are the results of task T5.3 "Deployment of Industry lab use case". Deliverable D5.3 is developed in an iterative approach, and the present document is the second version (M24) of it whereas the first version was delivered on M16 of the project. This version of the deliverable includes besides the planning related activities, the deployment and the operational phase of the developments at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. The first version was focused on the planning for the implementation of the developments utilizing the results of D1.2 "Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description" where the needs of the workers and their requirements for a shop floor with enhance operations is described.

This second version of the Deliverable D5.3 verifies and in some cases corrects some of the described actions of the first iteration of D5.3 on M18. Some of the components that were installed at the shop floor needed additional actions, upgrades and corrections in order to be compliant with the needs of the workers. Thus, the role of this Deliverable is very important not only for the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI but for all three shop floors, because the functionality of many of the components of SatisFactory is validated and after that they could be set up at the other two shop floors.

1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a specific description of the roadmap for implementation of each Business Scenario that is determined for CERTH/CPERI shop floor, the status of the tools that are “version 1” or “version 2” (M24) deployed at the shop floor and the deployment plan for each involved component in order to fulfill the user requirements and needs. The developments of D5.3 cover the activities and procedures that took place at the selected Business Scenarios dealing with Chemical Processes according to the needs of the involved end user (CERTH/CPERI). More specifically the two versions of D5.3 cover:

- **1st version (M16):** Planning of Scenario realization focusing on deployment/preparation of SatisFactory platform (components, tools, services, interfaces) and installation of infrastructures to the CERTH/CPERI shop-floor.
- **2nd version (M24):** Implementation of the Business Scenarios using the SatisFactory platform and user engagement using all the provided tools from the technology

1.1 PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE

The purpose of this deliverable is to give a systematic methodology and a time schedule of the implementation of the Business Scenarios as performed by the selected groups of workers in conjunction with the usage of the appropriate SatisFactory platform components that are necessary in order for the operations to be successfully executed at CERTH/CPERI. The overall activities are guided by the high-level procedures and the use cases as analysed at D1.2 “Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description” in order to address existing issues or barriers related to the knowledge sharing and the collaboration of actors among the various locations at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

The roadmap for the implementation activities in this deliverable reflects the work performed in Task T5.3 – “Deployment of Industry lab use case”, with a close collaboration with the activities of Tasks T1.2 – “Models for actors and procedures interconnection” and T1.3 – “Use Cases and Scenarios” where the analysis and definition of the business scenarios, the use cases and the identification of the involved actor groups took place. Also, there is a strong synergy with the activities of Task T5.1 - “SatisFactory Components Integration and Framework”.

The **main objectives** of the activities that were performed at Task T5.3 “Deployment of Industry lab use case” for the 1st version of D5.3 are:

- Definition of the methodology for preparation for implementation of the Business Scenarios and a time schedule for the implementation
- Selection of group of actors to be informed and participate in the preparatory activities
- Set-up and installation of the SatisFactory components and the available tools from the technology partners (until M15) at the CERTH/CPERI industrial shop-floor.
- Setup of the infrastructure for the software related components
- Preliminary tests for validation of the provided functionalities by the tools
- Engaging actors to use the available tools at the shop-floor.
- Develop the appropriate environment to implement parts/sections of the Business Scenarios

- Capture, analyse and communicate end-user needs for the proposed tools in an effective manner.

The developments of Deliverable D5.3 were be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that lead to the production of a total of two releases of this document, respectively in Project Months M16 and M24. The development of this deliverable was coordinated by CERTH with contribution of ABE, FIT, ISMB, REGOLA, EPFL and GLASSUP.

1.2 BACKGROUND

The background of the work performed and described in this deliverable is related to the 3rd phase of the project “Prototyping, Implementation and System Integration” and aims at the implementation of the Business Scenarios at CERTH/CPERI shop floor using the tools delivered by the technology providing partners of the project and the engaging of the workers within the activities of the scenarios. Figure 1 shows the relationship between Task T5.3 and the other tasks/WPs in the project.

Figure 1: Activities and Connection of D5.3 with other tasks and WPs

As CERTH/CPERI is the pre-industrial environment most of the SatisFactory components and tools are be initially tested at a small scale using the prototypes which are be built during the project. More specifically, deliverable D5.3 results from activities of WP5 – “Integration, Deployment, Industrial Trials Demonstration and Evaluation”, which is responsible for the integration and actual implementation of the tools and application environment for a safer and more attractive shop floor to address the need and requirements of the end users at the shop floor. Within WP 5, task T5.3 focuses on the planning and deployment of the SatisFactory developments at CERTH/CPERI shop-

floor utilizing the components and tools from SatisFactory platform. There exists a strong synergy among deliverable D5.3, derived by the activities of task T5.3, and other tasks in WP5 and other work packages within the project (WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4). Furthermore, inputs from other tasks that run in parallel are required in order to deploy and implement the Business Scenarios (BSCs) that address the needs of the end users at CETH/CPERI, as documented at deliverable D1.1 “User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and deployment guidelines”. The output from this deliverable will be evaluated according to the test described at D5.2 “Evaluation Plan” and will be documented at D5.5 “Final System Evaluation Report”.

Initially the deployment activities which deals mostly with the planning for the deployment and the testing of the components and tools that are available to be used is described. Subsequently, the testing and final deployment of the components are documented.

1.3 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

Following this introductory section, the remaining part of the document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 provides a general overview of the approach and methodology for planning of implementation and the context of the CETH/CPERI shop floor where the tools are be implemented.
- Chapter 3 describes the tools that are used at every BSCs which is related to the CETH/CPERI shop floor including their deployment status along with requirements and implementation pre-requisites.
- Chapter 4 includes the planning, the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-5.1 - Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction” that deals with corrective actions that need immediate attention at the various pilot plants at the shop-floor and perform works to repair or replace a faulty or degraded equipment.
- Chapter 5 includes the planning, the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-5.2 - Startup procedures for pilot plants” that deals with the critical start-up procedures of operating hydroprocessing pilot plants using proper Standard Operating Procedures (SOP).
- Chapter 6 includes the planning, the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-5.3 - Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures” that deals with the Improvement of the process workflow for the reconfiguration of a multipurpose unit.
- Chapter 7 includes the planning, the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-6.1 Recognition of incidents and path optimization for workers movement on the shop floor” that demonstrates the usage of advanced SatisFactory tools to identify incidents at the shop floor related to workers and undesired conditions identified at areas where workers are present targeting the increase of the safety and comfort of the involved actors.
- Finally, Chapter 8 provides general conclusions and guidelines on how the results included in this deliverable will be further elaborated in forthcoming stages of the project activities within the scope of WP5.

This document is supported by one annex that contains the detailed steps of the Standard Operating Procedures with respective photos and connections for two of the scenarios related to CERTH/CPERI (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.3).

2 GENERIC APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY FOR PLANNING OF IMPLEMENTATION

The goal of Chapter 2 is to describe the planning methodology towards the deployment of SatisFactory tools at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor in order to realize the scenarios that were derived by the use needs and requirements. The main objective is to enhance and enrich CERTH/CPERI shop-floor environment integrating key enabling technologies such as intelligent decision support systems (iDSS), augmented reality, wearable and ubiquitous computing as well as and customised social communication platforms coupled with experience design and gamification-based techniques for the efficient transfer of knowledge and collaboration among the workers.

The deployed solutions are categorized using hardware and software, simple and/or complex solutions. The use of the respective set of components will be used to realize and optimize the interactive selected procedures that are performed by the group of workers. Overall the activities for the planning and implementation of SatisFactory developments are organized according to the Business Scenarios that are described in detail at D1.2 “Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description”. Table 1 summarizes the list of the SatisFactory high level Business Scenarios that are developed for CERTH/CPERI shop-floor.

Table 1 List of CERTH/CPERI Business Scenarios and Application Scenarios

Business Scenario	Application Scenario	Name
BSC-5	Online supervision of the operation and workforce resources of pilot plants for chemical processes (CERTH)	
	BSC-5.1	Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction
	BSC-5.2	Startup procedures for pilot plants
	BSC-5.3	Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures
BSC-6	Recognition of incidents and path optimization for workers’ movement (CERTH)	
	BSC-6.1	Recognition of incidents and path optimization for workers movement on the shop floor

In brief the needs and requirements at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor and their connection to the scenarios are summarized to:

- Active collaboration between the various groups of actors (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.2, BSC-5.3)
- Sharing of knowledge from the shop floor to the process supervisor and the director that would improve the decision making procedure in terms of time, effort and global view of each unit (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.2)
- Improvement of the planned maintenance actions by acquiring flow diagrams and electrical schematics depending on the unit, involved subsystem or device (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.3)

- Re-adaptation of the production setup of a continuous process unit based on client’s needs and previously used configurations (BSC-5.3)
- Efficient and fast response at unplanned events based on an augmented interface that would derive online in near real-time information depending the specific problem (BSC-5.1)
- Minimize the safety-related incidents which are caused by erroneous human actions (BSC-6.1)

According to the needs and requirements of BSC-5 and BSC-6, the available SatisFactory platform components are initially installed and afterwards used by the involved workers. Therefore, the activities described in the next chapters are related to the analysis of the tools to be used from the SatisFactory platform (by technology providing partners – CERTH/ITI, ABE, ISMB, REGOLA, EPFL, FIT, GLASSUP) that focus on deployment/testing of the tools. Also in the first stages of T5.3 there was a preliminary engagement of selected actors (both operators and technicians) to test the available functionalities provided by the tools. In the later stages of T5.3 more actors were involved, to test the effectiveness and the responsiveness of the tools.

2.1 SHOP FLOOR AREA FOR THE DEPLOYMENT OF THE SCENARIOS

CERTH/CPERI shop-floor has a wide range of industrial automation systems and industrial software platforms. The automated systems are used for process control and remote monitoring (SCADA, DCS, PLC based). CERTH/CPERI’s selected shop-floor processes are used as a test bed for SatisFactory products and solutions. Figure 2 shows the highlighted areas where the scenarios are be deployed focusing in different perspectives and by engaging all the group of workers of CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

Figure 2 Overview of CERTH/CPERI shop floor and designated areas where the business scenarios are performed

Figure 3: Partial overview of CERTH/CPERI's shop floor and plants

Within SatisFactory project, CERTH/CPERI utilizes its industrial automation infrastructure for the deployment of the integrated Reference Architecture Platform to CERTH/CPERI's process plants where the Industrial Lab cases are deployed. CERTH/CPERI's infrastructure consists of numerous experimental industrial process systems where information is propagated through a network backbone that facilitates data exchange from and to the input/output field of respective units. Each unit has sensors that acquire various signals which are distributed in a wide area and are connected using industrial networks. Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA) for chemical and energy production processes are in operation with respective middleware software.

Figure 4 CERTH/CPERI's Monitoring and control HMIs

CERTH/CPERI has developed and supports a wide multi-sensorial network of heterogeneous distributed systems (indicative industrial protocols: CANBus, Profibus, EtherCat, RS485). The monitoring and control is performed in real time and cover actions and events that take place throughout the life cycle of the information, starting from the encoding at the physical layer to the knowledge sharing to the end user. In order to provide a uniform way of communication at the application layer between the various sources and sinks of data, OPC-based interfaces are developed and deployed at each individual process unit.

2.2 PLANNING OF IMPLEMENTATION

In order to deploy SatisFactory solutions to CERTH/CPERI shop-floor there are a list of activities that had to take place in order to be compliant with the industrial-grade specifications for using new tools at the shop-floor. The following is a summary of the implementation process, which was followed by

CERTH/CPERI personnel in collaboration with the technology providing partners of SatisFactory consortium. The scope of the whole process was that CERTH/CPERI team:

- ensures that the design objectives and intent are clearly documented.
- performs a focused review of design specifications of the tools to be used.
- CERTH/CPERI personnel develop an Implementation Plan.
- conducts various scoping meetings where the implementation process is reviewed with the technology providing partners and schedules additional meetings, as necessary, throughout set-up, to plan, coordinate, and schedule future activities and resolve deployment problems.
- works with the technology providing partners in developing start-up plans and start-up documentation formats. The technological partners provide the pre functional checklists to be completed during the startup process.

The technology providing partners executed and documented the pre-functional checklists and perform startup and local or remote configuration. CERTH/CPERI team documented that the checklists and startup were completed according to the approved plans. This may include the engaging of actors from the shop-floor besides the development CERTH/CPERI team. In general, performance verification proceeded from simple to complex, from component level to tools and integrated bundled tools, with pre-functional checklists being completed before functional testing. Tools and software documentation were submitted to the CERTH/CPERI team during normal submittals, including detailed set-up procedures.

2.2.1 Methodology for Planning and Stages

The purpose of D5.3 is to define the process to be followed in the delivery and handover of SatisFactory systems and components into operation at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor. This section describes the elements that are considered towards commencement of the tools and components that are utilized by the workers to implement their daily activities in an improved manner and in active collaboration with the other actors within the shop-floor. The key stages towards implementation are identified along with the order in which these shall be addressed. The key stages are defined below as:

- Stage 1 Design of components – Preparatory actions (Factory Acceptance Tests)
- Stage 2 Set-up at the shop floor (Site Acceptance Testing)
- Stage 3 Deployment and Commissioning
- Stage 4 Operation and Maintenance

Each stage of the implementation process includes a list of actions that need to be in place before the next stage of the process is commenced. At the next sections a specific timeframe for the realization of the aforementioned stages is delivered. As SatisFactory project is related to innovation actions a minor deviation from the exact schedule is anticipated and the finally realized stages are documented in this 2nd version of the deliverable. Also, since the implementation involves workers and the modification of their daily activities, a careful approach to manage the resistance to change is necessary.

2.2.2 Activities and aspects addressed for the Implementation

Towards the deployment for operation of the SatisFactory platform the following activities were performed by the involved technology providing partners in collaboration with the CERTH/CPERI team. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to give examples of the requirements on a typical scheme. The following aspects are addressed by the implementation team:

- Coordinate and direct the implementation activities in a logical, sequential and efficient manner using consistent protocols and forms, centralized documentation and clear and regular communications and consultations with all necessary partners.
- Ensure that the design objectives and intent are clearly documented and carried out in the design and set-up stages.
- Develop clear deployment specifications and the functional testing requirements included in the delivered documents.
- Before startup, gather and review the current sequences/operations.
- Approve pre functional tests by reviewing pre functional checklist reports or by direct site observation.
- Coordinate, witness, and approve functional performance tests performed by installing contractors.
- Coordinate re-testing as necessary until satisfactory performance is achieved.
- Oversee and approve the training of the operating workers.
- Provide a final implementation report, which includes:
 - a. An executive summary, list of participants and roles, brief shop-floor area description, overview of implementation and testing scope, and a general description of testing and verification methods.
 - b. For each components or bundles of components, the report contains documentation and training meetings in the following areas:
 - 1) SatisFactory components shop-floor specific specifications,
 - 2) SatisFactory components installation,
 - 3) Functional performance and efficiency,
 - 4) SatisFactory components documentation context of use, and
 - 5) Operator training.All outstanding non-compliance items shall be specifically listed.
 - c. Recommendations for improvement, future actions, process changes, etc. will also be listed. Each non-compliance issue shall be referenced to the specific functional test, inspection, etc. where the deficiency is documented.
 - d. The functional performance and efficiency section for each piece of equipment, shall include a brief description of the verification method used including observations and conclusions from the feedback obtained by the involved actors.

During the setup and deployment stages the CERTH/CPERI team assisted with problem-solving or resolving non-conformance or deficiencies, but ultimately that responsibility resided with the technology providing partner. After notice to proceed from the CERTH/CPERI team, the up-to-date schedule is at the responsibility of the technology providing partners. The primary role of the planning is to develop and coordinate the execution of a testing plan and observe and document performance, that is, determined whether SatisFactory components/tools are in accordance with their functionalities described at deliverable D2.1 to fulfill the needs documents at deliverable D1.1

and implement the scenarios of deliverable D1.2. The evaluation scenarios and evaluation tests are detailed described at deliverable D5.2.

2.2.3 Time scheduling for each Business Scenario of CERTH/CPERI

An overview of the implementation of the Business Scenarios at the shop-floor is depicted at Figure 5. Since there are many components and tools involved at each scenario the phases are based on the latest delivered tool. So, each stage starts when at least one of the components is available for design, setup, deployment or operation. Therefore, the actual operation of each scenario is performed gradually. The engaging of the actors is also performed gradually, initially targeting at a small group and afterwards the selected involved actors will participate, as the tools will be integrated at their daily activities. At the 1st version of D5.3 the activities related to the implementation and initial testing are included, whereas the entire integrated scenario operation is documented at the 2nd version of D5.3 due to M24. The Gantt chart covers the activities performed until M24. The preliminary schedule is initially prepared with the knowledge that specific dates will change as deployment and the business scenarios are further progressed. The tools that have entered the operation phase will continue to be evaluated since the installation at the pre-pilot shop floor is their first working version. The final version of the components will be setup at the industrial partners at COMAU and SUNLIGHT premises.

Figure 5 Gantt diagram of the implementation phases of the Business scenarios at CETH/CPERI

SatisFactory components are documented at deliverable D2.1.2 “SatisFactory System Architecture”. To visualize which components are used for the realization of each scenario the architecture is used as a reference (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Components diagram of the overall SatisFactory architecture

Besides the technical details that covered at deliverable D5.1 “SatisFactory Components Integration and framework” there are various requirements and pre-requisites which is necessary to be covered in order for them to work as designed at the actual working environment which, in the case of D5.3 is CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

The hardware related infrastructure that is developed and is dedicated to SatisFactory platform at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor is summarized at Table 2.

Table 2 Dedicated infrastructure at CERTH/CPERI shop floor for SatisFactory platform

Type	Components installed
Server with windows OS (Win 7 pro 64 bits)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> iDSS LinkSmart
Server with Linux OS (Ubuntu 14.04 64 bits)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ontology manager
Server with windows OS (Win 7 pro 32 bits)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)
Server with windows OS (NUC pc Win 8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gesture and Content Recognition Manager (GCRM)
Raspberry PI mini pc with Linux OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Localization Devices & Manager
Raspberry PI mini pc with Linux OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature sensor (Thermal sensor network)

2.3 BUSINESS SCENARIOS AND ARCHITECTURE COMPONENTS

In order to assess the Business Scenarios and their connection with the Satisfactory platform a template was circulated to all partners that includes information related to the component usage, the restrictions/prerequisites and the feasibility of each component to be used at the specific Business Scenario. The purpose of the gathered information is to ensure that the provided components would be able to be adjusted for the scope for the scenarios and to extract a first indication about the priorities and effort/complexity categorization. The provided information considered the context of implementation as described at the specific scenario.

A snapshot of the information that was collected for each component can be seen at Table 3 :

Table 3 Assessment of Business Scenarios and Components

A	B	C	D	E	F
Component name	Direct / Indirect	Effort required	Restrictions	Prerequisites	Feasibility (YES/NO)
Main Component X					
Subcomponent X.Y					

At the first column (A) there are the **categories** of the components and their subcategories. Next at second column (B) there are three options that can be selected from each components subcategory.

- i. Direct: When the Business Scenario uses this component
- ii. Indirect: When the Business Scenario uses this component through another component
- iii. No Usage: When the Business Scenario does not use this component at all

The third column (C) shows how effort required; from scale of 1-3 how difficult is it to incorporate the component to the Business Scenario. The **complexity and effort** which is documented for each component is not related to Person Months (PMs) but to the complexity of integration to the infrastructure of the shop floor. The specific value (1-3) is a measure of prioritization for the technology providing partners and it will assist the evaluation of the implementation aspects of each scenario. The next column (D) relates to the **restrictions** about each components subcategory:

- i. Potential Restrictions, e.g. need to have a specific data format? or size that is read or allowed to be stored?
- ii. Obstacles: language, or feed to specific DB such as Oracle, etc.

The fifth column (E) relates to the **prerequisites** of each components subcategory.

Finally the last column refers to the **feasibility** (YES/NO) of each subcategory. Based on this analysis, the Business Scenarios of the pre-pilot site, CETH/CPERI, were analysed and the technology providing partners evaluated the feasibility of their components to be implemented with respect to the Business Scenarios deployment. The same analyses will be performed for the Business Scenarios of the other two shop floors, Sunlight and COMAU, and will be presented at deliverable D5.4 "Industrial Pilots Set-up and Demonstration".

2.3.1 Business Scenarios and Component Usage

In order to analyse and describe the effect that the components will have to each of the Business Scenarios, a set of diagrams were developed. The following diagram shows the number of

components that each Business Scenario of CErTH/CPeRI shop floor is using. Each component performs a specific action and can work either as a stand alone or with an interaction with another component.

Figure 7 Number of components for the SatisFactory Business Scenarios at CErTH/CPeRI shop floor

2.3.2 Business Scenarios and Components' Implementation Effort

In addition to the above information, there was a need to review the effort that the technological partners will need in order to create the components that they are responsible for. This information is being available at the following diagram.

Figure 8 Component implementation effort per Business Scenario at CErTH/CPeRI shop floor

A very important issue that can be mentioned here is that most of the components require effort level 2 in order to be developed.

Figure 9: Summary of “Effort level” needed for the components installed at CERTH/CPERI premises

A summary of “Effort level” needed for the components of SatisFactory can be seen at Figure 9. It is clear that the most of the components require effort level 2 and components that require effort level 1 or 3 are almost the same number. From Figure 9 it is evident that most of the components have normal implementation needs and requirements as defined by the technology providing partner, which is a first indication that the business scenarios will be successfully implemented.

2.3.3 Remarks for Implementation and Set-up procedures at CERTH/CPERI

Overall the technology providing partners verified the feasibility for delivering their components and tools at the CERTH/CPERI shop-floor in order to be used to implement the operations and functions described at the scenarios. The status and usage the involved components are analyzed at a scenario basis in the following chapters. The information within D5.3 is according to the technical input provided by the partner responsible for the development and delivery of the components/tools. The set-up is performed in close collaboration among the provider and the CERTH/CPERI team, whereas the base infrastructure and the mounting of the equipment at the final position was done by CERTH/CPERI personnel according to the regulations for safety and in compliance with the regulation for commissioning equipment to shop-floors with chemical pilot plants. More specifically the set-up was performed either by local presence or remotely through the appropriate tools for accessing the infrastructures and the servers that are dedicated for SatisFactory project.

3 PLANNING AND DEPLOYMENT OF COMPONENTS USED BY MULTIPLE SCENARIOS

The demonstration of the capabilities and functionalities of SatisFactory platform is verified through the implementation of the aforementioned BSCs that cover the identified needs and requirements of the involved actors at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. The goal of Chapter 3 is to describe the planning for implementation and the status of the SatisFactory components and tools that are used in multiple scenarios using a common infrastructure. They are described in this chapter in order to avoid repetition of information which is similar to all cases.

As previously mentioned the SatisFactory platform that is installed at the involved shop floor consists of several components. Some of them are being used at all the Business Scenarios and some of the only at specific Business Scenarios. Therefore, we have two cases about their usage:

- a) To all scenarios or
- b) By the involved workers at the shop floor for activities that are performed to various scenarios.

Table 4 presents the components that are common to all business scenarios and some components that have functionalities that are used by all actors of the shop floor. According to the scenario they provide different functionalities for the end-user at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor and they are utilized within the context of the procedures performed at each different scenarios. Also as they constitute the basis for the SatisFactory platform (CIDEM, Middleware, etc.) they are parametrically configured to delivered the requested function upon demand. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 4: Identified Components to be utilized in all BSCs at CERTH/CPERI shop floor

Responsible partner	
CERTH	<p>Component: Repository – Asset Machinery, Production Models</p> <p>Restrictions: All data coming to the Repository from other components must be in xml format, compliant with the B2MML standard</p> <p>Prerequisites: Intranet connection between Repository and the other components</p>
EPFL	<p>Component: Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: Data coming from CIDEM should filter and then loaded within the OM. A mirror copy of the SF repository is not needed. Every dataset have to be Extracted, Transformed, Loaded (ETL) according to a specific allowed format, for instance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •RDF+XML, RDF+N3, structJSON, structXML, ironJSON, commON <p>OM repository size shouldn't be too big in order not to introduce unhelpful time delay.</p> <p>Prerequisites: CIDEM Data have to be available in a format that can be transformed into triplets.</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Suggestions for Improvement platform – “My Factory” – Gamification-based tools</p> <p>Restrictions: The “My Factory” component is to be used via a tablet at a fixed station. It cannot be accessed outside the factory site.</p> <p>Prerequisites: Categories for suggestions are predefined.</p>

FIT	<p>Component: Suggestions for Improvement platform – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools</p> <p>Restrictions: The “My Factory Management” component can only be accessed by the management using their office PCs or laptops. It cannot be accessed outside the factory site.</p> <p>Prerequisites: Categories for suggestions and at least one responsible person for each category is predefined.</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools</p> <p>Restrictions: In order to utilize the gamification framework, each external framework is required to create a game and define the points against each task to be performed by the workers.</p> <p>Prerequisites: The actions related to the external systems that are to be included as tasks in a game are identified beforehand. Rewards, avatars, points and badges are specified beforehand.</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools</p> <p>Restrictions: The worker can only view his own points. If he desires to view the cumulative team score, he has to view it on the digital screen at the factory site.</p> <p>Prerequisites: For the app to be useful in conveying the current score of the worker, there has to be at least one external system linked to the gamification framework.</p>
ISMB	<p>Component: Middleware – Device Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: Device manager is involved in the case of usage of some environmental data acquisition device. It should be technically possible to integrate involved devices through the device manager</p> <p>Prerequisites: Involved devices API and usage manual availability</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Middleware - Core Services</p> <p>Restrictions: Device Managers and Services are registered into LinkSmart eco-system</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Middleware - Event Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: MQTT protocol is used for publishing and event notification. Message payload is CIDEM compliant</p> <p>Prerequisites: Services needs to learn the designated topics LinkSmart catalogue services, those being configured in a Registration Document by Device Managers</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Middleware - Event Aggregator</p> <p>Restrictions: Store received subscription notifications into CIDEM repository with CIDEM compliant format</p> <p>Prerequisites: CIDEM Repository REST interface is available</p>

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

3.1 REPOSITORY – ASSET MACHINERY, PRODUCTION MODELS

The repository constitutes the basis of the SatisFactory platform. In the Repository, there is a need to store information about the static and the dynamic information that is related to the shop-floor operation, such as physical assets required for the operation of the specific part of the pilot plant, the topology of the overall shop floor, restricted/dangerous areas in it, measurements, events, etc.


```

160.40.51.98:8080/cidem/resources/cidem/getActorList?shopFloorID=CPERI
Most Visited My daily checks CERTH

This XML file does not appear to have any style information associated with it. The document tree is shown below.

- <CIDEM>
  - <ShopFloor>
    <ShopFloorID>CPERI</ShopFloorID>
    - <SFInformationModel>
      - <ActorsList>
        - <Actor>
          <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
          - <b2mml:Description>
            Overall supervision on the workflow of the shop floor
          </b2mml:Description>
          - <b2mml:Person>
            <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
            <b2mml:Description>Managers and Engineers</b2mml:Description>
          </b2mml:Person>
          - <b2mml:PersonnelClass>
            <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
            <b2mml:Description>Stakeholders</b2mml:Description>
          - <b2mml:PersonnelClassProperty>
            <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
            <b2mml:Description>Floor Manager</b2mml:Description>
          </b2mml:PersonnelClassProperty>
          </b2mml:PersonnelClass>
          - <b2mml:QualificationTestSpecification>
            <b2mml:ID>2</b2mml:ID>
            <b2mml:Description>Experienced</b2mml:Description>
          </b2mml:QualificationTestSpecification>
        </Actor>
      + <Actor></Actor>
      + <Actor></Actor>
      + <Actor></Actor>
      + <Actor></Actor>
      + <Actor></Actor>
      + <Actor></Actor>
    
```

Figure 10: Information of CERTH/CPERI actors that are stored at repository

This component doesn't have a user interface because it is running at the background supporting the communication a data exchange of the other components. The figure above shows a manual data retrieval from the repository, presenting information about the actors of CERTH/CPERI.

This information has been set out according to the agreed known standards as well as custom fields for specific technical information (i.e. configuration files) so that it can be recognizable and retractable. Thus, the information for such models (i.e. equipment, assets, actors, procedures, measurements, etc.) has been grouped following the hierarchy of the machinery components, subcomponents and topology, as well as the associations with the production activities.

Table 5: Information of the Status and the required input of the CIDEM

Status
The final models have been defined and agreed, as well as specific details on the types to be adopted and used, in collaboration with other components too. All components that communicate with the Repository have finalized the implementation of accessing/retrieving/storing information.

Required input

The final version of the Repository is available and supports all of the discussed protocols and standards. Necessary modifications that were needed are needed towards expanding these models into a common framework in order to fully support the SatisFactory framework. A small set of the Models is needed by M17, so that this sub-component's second version is available by M19 to be tested at the Industry Lab from M20 and on.

3.2 ONTOLOGY MANAGER

The Ontology Manager was designed as a **Multi-Layered Ontology Network**. Three so-called shop floor oriented ontologies, i.e. COMAU_Ontology, SUNLIGHT_Ontology and CERTH_Ontology, can be considered as the **Top Level**. The latter aims to model and then represent the knowledge concerning each specific shop floor and their Business Scenarios (BSCs). In particular, pieces of knowledge and shop floor information data vocabularies are collected, modelled, and managed within a knowledge-base by taking into particular consideration the optimization of the human resources, which is the aim of the T2.2. Then, the **Middle Level** contains the so-called SatisFactory Upper Ontology. This mostly focuses on the three main shop floor concepts, such as *Assets*, *Procedures* and *Workers* and aims to provide a shared vocabulary by bridging the domain-specific ontologies at the top level to the so-called data-oriented ontologies at the lowest level. The **Low Level**, in fact, contains these data-oriented ontologies that have been derived from the CIDEM XML schemas. For this reason, this layer mostly adheres to the information data structure and was labelled as CIDEM_Ontology.

The following figure presents an instance of the Ontology Manager editor, in particular, here it is possible to see the three OM layers together with the first level of sub-concepts (ontology classes).

Figure 11: The Ontology Manager Editor

So far, according to the methodology that has been exploited to develop the semantic models for SatisFactory (described in D2.2), the BSC5 is investigated as a whole. Moreover, BSC-5.1, BSC-5.2 and BSC-5.3 share most of the concepts and knowledge sources. Thus, the actual BSC5 semantic model conceives of concepts that are described in the following table.

Table 6: Semantic Model of BSC-5

Concept	Description
<i>Worker</i>	Supervisors and Managers Operators and Technicians
<i>Pilot plant</i>	Small dedicated industrial system
<i>Procedure</i>	Planned activity to perform within the pilot plant
<i>Data</i>	Information data, can be either static or dynamic (often called “functions”)
<i>Component</i>	Simple component of the pilot plant
<i>Physical Asset</i>	Equipment, inventory or machines
<i>Action</i>	Action performed by the worker toward the completion of a specific procedure

The BSC-6.1 semantic model is focused on the concepts and relations that must be explicit in the context of workers safety. In particular, such ontology model conceives of concepts that are related with the areas in which workers are working in order to support the patch optimization for workers' movement. The main classes (concepts) of the model are described below.

Table 7: Semantic Model of BSC-6

Concept	Description
<i>Worker</i>	Operators and Technicians
<i>Pilot Plant</i>	Small dedicated industrial system
<i>Area</i>	Accessible or Forbidden Area
<i>Action</i>	Action performed by the user

Just like the other semantic models, these concepts drives the semantic lifting of the XML data and put the basis for a semantics-driven querying process of shopfloor information and knowledge that supports the end user in the application scenarios mentioned above.

Table 8: Information of the Status and the required input of the OM

Status
<p>The Semantic Framework has been already installed and tested on a remote PC at CERTH and can be access from the following IP: 160.40.51.99 through a Drupal-based UI.</p> <p>The ontology models were initially created on local machines through the use of non-commercial academic software, such as Protégé. The CIDEM ontology allows the semantic lifting of the xml data that are stored into the SatisFactory repository. Information transformed into RDF triples according to the semantic structures defined in the Ontology Manager are then stored in a proper RDF store that should be perceived as a knowledge base for the whole SatisFactory components.</p> <p>First tests of the Ontology Manager were scheduled on M16 (end of April 2016) and helped the further development and ramification of the semantic structures and characterization of RDF data flow. On M18 the last version of the ontology structure was, hence, released and deployed on http://160.40.51.99/ontology_manager.</p> <p>The collection of data coming from the shop floor, then, allowed the test and deployment of the OM and SPARWL query engine that can be accessed on http://160.40.51.99/om_engine and http://160.40.51.99/content/sparql.</p> <p>The latter has been finally deployed on M20 according to the DoW and the SatisFactory schedule. In this framework, two additional functionalities have been also implemented in the OM, which give the end-user the possibility to visualize pre-set SPARQL query results as graphs http://160.40.51.99/graphs and visualize the network of ontological concepts http://160.40.51.99/sites/all/libraries/webvowl_0.5.2/index.html.</p>
Required input
<p>Sample data has been already provided by CERTH for testing purposes.</p> <p>The interaction of the Ontology Manager with downstream components, for example, the iDSS and</p>

the TDAT, requires the collection of more data. However, the semantic model has been designed to support most of the xml data, which are managed by the CIDEM.

Results of Operation

The Ontology Manager has been already delivered and described on D3.1 by the end of M20. A few updates will be carried out according to eventual new end-user needs.

3.3 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT PLATFORM – MY FACTORY – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

The “My Factory Management” component of the Suggestions for Improvement is a platform created for the management mainly for the purpose of taking decisions on the suggestions submitted by the workers in order to improve the process. The suggestions are assigned to different categories and for each category there is person responsible for taking decisions. The responsible person can also collaborate with others to take a decision, if needed. This component is integrated into the Social Collaboration Platform, making use of its user roles to the end of user rights management.

Table 9: Information of the Status of the gamification tools

Status
The prototyping and user evaluations for the “My Factory Management” component are complete. It is currently in data model design phase.

Results of operation

The initial version of the “My Factory” component of Suggestions for Improvement on Social Collaboration Platform has been deployed by the end of November (M23). Further optimizations will be updated by the finalization of T2.3. The component was also installed on a standalone touchscreen installation, tested and performed as expected.

Figure 12: Suggestions for Improvement Platform on the Social and Collaboration web Platform

3.4 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT PLATFORM – MY FACTORY MANAGEMENT – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

3.4.1 Administrative Environment in Gamification Framework

The Suggestions for improvement platform and its interconnection with the Gamification platform required an administrative environment in order to create the gamified processes. This environment has been implemented and it is deployed to pilot plant CPERI which used it in order to create its games. The main view of the administrative environment is shown only to the user that has administrative privileges and has the ability to create these games. The following picture shows the design of gamification's admin tab:

Figure 13: Gamification's Administrative Environment User Interface

The manager of each component that is using Gamification Platform defines who is going to be the administrator. Gamification platform is configurable as long as the design of games is concerned. By clicking on Admin tab, the administrator is facing the “add new Game” button for giving a customized title and description of the game. After creation, the game appears in the admin tab for further implementation as well as in My Profile-> Status tab of Social Collaboration for joining it. As it is presented in Figure 13, for each game created there is the ability to add:

- Quests
- Actions
- Rules
- Rewards
- Leaderboards
- Participants

Quests: A quest is actually a mission that is active for some time interval defined by the administrator. It is time based and it orders to gain the reward assigned to it, the player should fulfil it during this time interval. For example, answer 6 questions in one day to take one day off.

Actions: An action is a complete task that describes a job which has to be done. Every game must have at least one action in order to be played. For example, ask a question or answer a question.

Rules: Rules are the base of the gamification engine as they define exactly how the actions should be done and what rewards are gained after fulfilment. Actions are entities completely independent from points/sets because the latter are also separate entity that can be combined in all possible ways in the rule session. Rules check how many times an action has been triggered and if the player has already some reward or level of experience. For example, if the action “answer question” has been triggered 1 time, give the player 10 points. Additionally, if the player has 250 points give her the golden cup. If the player has the golden cup and is It Technician give her the golden keyboard.

Rewards: A reward is the profit of the successfully completeness of an action. It can be one of the following types:

- Scalar (e.g. Points)
- Set (e.g. Cups, Medals)
- Status(e.g. Novice, Master)
- Compound(A combination of the above e.g. Golden Cup and status Master)

Leader boards: Leader boards are the cumulative representation of points that are gained for each player, showed by order. The player can see above her and below her how far her co-workers are according to their scores. Not all players appear in leader boards, but only the 3 before and after the one whose profile is logged in.

Participants: Here is the list of all the players that have joined the game.

Every game can have a cover photo uploaded as well as every reward in order to have a fancier environment of interaction.

The entities which are described above have the CRUD actions implemented.

Table 10: Information of the Status and the results of operation of the Gamification’s Administrative Environment

Status
The prototyping and user evaluations for the “My Factory Management” component are complete. It is currently in data model design phase and optimization until the end of T2.3
Results of operation
It is an independent component that doesn’t require any input from any other external system. However, it shares the database with the “My Factory” component for having a shared pool of suggestions.

3.5 GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

The gamification framework is a central framework used to manage all the details of the gamification to be implemented at the factory. This means that the gamification framework provides certain APIs to the external systems e.g. Suggestions Platform, in order to enable them to create games, add tasks to these games and allocate points to these tasks. The gamification framework consists of a database that contains all the data related to all the games created by all the external systems utilizing the gamification framework. The cumulative scores are communicated to the workers via the digital screen and individual points via the “What’s My Score” component.

Table 11: Information of the Status and the required input of the gamification framework

Status
The prototyping and user evaluations for the Gamification Framework are complete. Currently some

last adjustments are made in connection with the Administrative Environment component integrated into the collaboration platform.

Required input

An initial version of the “the Gamification Framework was deployed by the end of August (M20). An updated version has been deployed by the end of November (M23). The Gamification Framework works as intended while minor updates will continue being deployed until the end of T2.5.

3.5.1 Suggestions for Improvement Kiosk

The Suggestions for Improvement Kiosk is a platform created for the workers on the shopfloor, mainly for the purpose of submitting suggestions to improve the process. Workers can also view suggestions submitted by others. It is an alternative UI to the Suggestions for Improvement component present also in the “My Factory” Social Collaboration Platform.

Figure 14: Suggestions for Improvement Platform Kiosk app

Table 12: Information of the Status of the gamification tools

Status

The prototyping and user evaluations for the “My Factory” component are complete. Currently some last adjustment are made in connection with the “My Factory Management” component integrated into the collaboration platform.

Results of operation

An initial version of the “My Factory” component of Suggestions for Improvement Platform was deployed by the end of August (M20). An updated version has been deployed by the end of November (M23). The gamification module works as intended while minor updates will continue being deployed until the end of T2.5. (M30).

3.5.2 Gamified Processes deployed in CERN/CPERICPERI Social Collaboration Platform

The following processes have been gamified in CPERI in order to motivate participation, engagement and loyalty. The main factor of choosing a process to gamify is the completeness either in one or more steps.

Table 13: List of Gamified processes at CERN/CPERICPERI

Game Name	Gamified Process	Rule for Points	Points
Tips & Tricks	Ask a Question	If action AskQuestion has been triggered 1 time	20
	Answer a Question	If action AnswerQuestion has been triggered 1 time	30
	Vote a Question	If action VoteQuestion has been triggered 1 time	5
	Vote an Answer	If action VoteAnswer has been triggered 1 time	10
AIMMS All Actors	Start a Task	If action startTask has been triggered 1 time	5
	Finish a Task	If action endTask has been triggered 1 time	10
	Add Remarks	If action addRemarks has been triggered 1 time	15
AIMMS Process Technicians	Start a Task	If action startTask has been triggered 1 time	5
	Finish a Task	If action endTask has been triggered 1 time	10
	Add Remarks	If action addRemarks has been triggered 1 time	15
AIMMS IT Technicians	Start a Task	If action startTask has been triggered 1 time	5
	Finish a Task	If action endTask has been triggered 1 time	10

	Add Remarks	If action addRemarks has been triggered 1 time	15
AIMMS Process Operators	Start a Task	If action startTask has been triggered 1 time	5
	Finish a Task	If action endTask has been triggered 1 time	10
	Add Remarks	If action addRemarks has been triggered 1 time	15

In the gamified processes which are connected with the iDSS component, after collecting a specified amount of points, each player according to the group he/she belongs, gains special awards which appear in his/her personal profile in the Social Platform.

This process is defined by additional rules which check if the player satisfies the requirements of gaining the award.

Table 14: Additional rules for CERTH/CPERI gamified processes

Actor Group	Award	Rule for Award	Points	Action
All Actors	Bronze Medal	If player actorId has points in action	100	Finish a Task
	Silver Medal	If player actorId has points in action	150	Finish a Task
	Golden Medal	If player actorId has points in action	200	Finish a Task
	Bronze Cup	If player actorId has points in action	50	Start a Task
	Silver Cup	If player actorId has points in action	100	Start a Task
	Golden Cup	If player actorId has points in action	150	Start a Task
	Golden Crown	If the player has the max points in a month	Max	_____
Process Technicians	Bronze Hammer	If player actorId has points in action	50	Start a Task
	Silver Hammer	If player actorId has points in action	100	Start a Task
	Golden Hammer	If player actorId has points in action	200	Start a Task
IT Technicians	Bronze	If player actorId has points in	50	Start a Task

	Keyboard	action		
	Silver Keyboard	If player actorId has points in action	100	Start a Task
	Golden Keyboard	If player actorId has points in action	200	Start a Task
Process Operators	Bronze Gear	If player actorId has points in action	50	Start a Task
	Silver Gear	If player actorId has points in action	100	Start a Task
	Bronze Gear	If player actorId has points in action	200	Start a Task

Tips & Tricks is a way of encouraging the exchange of knowledge between colleagues because the gamification platform has rules to grade differently when a player asks a question and when she answers one. Moreover, it gives the opportunity to distinguish the best answers by voting them up and gaining points as well as marking the most common questions by voting them too and gaining points too.

While AIMMS targets in the more active participation in daily jobs, by grading their fulfilment with points and awards. Awards, as shown in the above table, are gained after completing actions for more than one times. So, if the player wants to earn the golden keyboard for example, she has to be an IT Technician and complete tasks that address to 200 points. Tasks in games are assigned from the administrator of the platform depending on the needs of the working environment and the capability of the human resources.

Table 15: Information of the Status and the Results of Operation of the gamified process

Status
The prototyping and user evaluations for the Gamified Processes deployed in CPERI Social Collaboration Platform are complete.
Results of operation
An initial version of the Gamification Framework was deployed by the end of August (M20). The final pilot installation was completed in November 2016 (M23)
The gamification module works as intended while minor updates will continue being deployed until the end of T2.5. (M30)

3.6 GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK – “WHAT’S MY SCORE” APP – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

In the social platform the user, after having created an account, can see the available games in the profile tab. Additionally if he/she has joined the game, a remark appears next to the name of the

game, indicating the amount of points she has gained so far. If the player wants to stop participating in the game he/she just have to click the “LEAVE” button. However, the points gained so far are being maintained in case the player wants to participate again in the future.

Figure 15: Awards Interface

Moreover, there is the “Awards” choice where every player can see the awards he/she has gained from each game that has participated in.

Figure 16: User score interface

In “Challenges”, the player can see the quests that the administrator has assigned to him/her, or the quests that are active on that specific time interval. It corresponds to the Quests entities that the administrator creates from the admin environment.

Finally in “In the crowd” option the player sees the ranking of participants that are close to his/her points. The player can see the position he/she holds amongst the participants but with the limitation of viewing the 3 above and below him/her for ethical reasons.

Table 16: Information of the Status and the Results of Operation of the Gamification based tools

Status
The prototyping and user evaluations for the “WHAT’S MY SCORE” component deployed in CPERI Social Collaboration Platform are complete.
Results of operation
An initial version of the “WHAT’S MY SCORE” component was deployed by the end of August (M20). The final pilot installation was completed in November 2016 (M23)
The component works as intended while minor updates will continue being deployed until the end of T2.5. (M30)

3.7 GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK – AIMMS APP – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

The AIMMS App included in the gamification platform of the Satisfactory project consists of four different apps for each kind of worker. There is an App, called AIMMS Process Technicians, which is addressed to the process technicians of the shop floor. The second one is called AIMMS IT Technicians and is addressed to the IT personnel. The third App is AIMMS Process Operators and it is addressed to the operators of the different processes on the shop floor. The final game is named AIMMS all actors and it is responsible for all the different kinds of workers using the iDSS and it can be seen as a concentrated game of the previous three.

In the AIMMS games of the gamification platform, the points of the workers can be seen. The app is designed in a way, that when a worker joins the game, he/she earns different amount of points for each task. If a worker starts a task, he/she gains five points. When they end a task, they gain fifteen points and when they comment in one task they gain ten points. The point allocation was decided with the cooperation of the end user, CPERI, in order to account for their business strategy. It is noted that the allocation of points is a parameter that can change according to the priorities set by the end user.

Figure 17: Social Platform Screen - Gamification Framework

In the above screen, it is shown when a worker joins a game. Before someone joins the game, his/her points are deactivated and after joining, the points are shown on the screen. Workers do not gain points by simply joining a game. They should create, comment or end a task to earn points.

When a task is created on the online application by a worker, the service can detect the creation of the task. Then, the gamification framework is working behind in order to award the points to the worker according to the number of tasks created. The gamification application running in console mode is shown below.

Figure 18: Gamification app running on console mode

From the console, the number of total tasks is shown as well as which the last task was and when it was completed.

Table 17: Information of the Status and the required input of the AIMMS app in the gamification framework

Status
Currently, the app is in running phase, it has been implemented.
Required input
The app shows the individual points of each worker and their current avatar from the central database of the gamification framework.

Progress of delivery

An initial version of the Gamification Framework was deployed by the end of August 2016 (M20). The final version was delivered in December 2016 (M24).

3.8 MIDDLEWARE – DEVICE MANAGER

The Device Manager (DM) is a software component which provides integration of heterogeneous devices at middleware level (Linksmart). It is a set of components developed on the basis of specific technologies to be adapted, which have different implementations fulfilling the following functionalities:

- Implementation of technology-dependant APIs or protocols to handle specific IoT physical objects.
- Provisioning, over available networks and appropriate protocols (MQTT, REST, Web Services), actual devices data and measurements.
- Devices presence management and device resources availability propagation at middleware level (LinkSmart Resource Catalogue).

Table 18: Information of the Status and the required input of the Device Manager

Status
The DM has been integrated with UWB localization devices, Dependable Network Infrastructure single-radio node sensors and gesture and content recognition devices. It leverages the MQTT protocol to share data and the REST-based component to subscribe devices and related services on the Resource/Service Catalogue.
Required input
Apart from technology specific knowledge necessary to interact with involved devices, it was required the functional specification of Resource Catalogue and Service Catalogue.

Results of operation

The DM was integrated with the LinkSmart Catalog APIs “version 0.2.0” and distribution “version 0.2.0”. It was tested along with the single components during their testing.

3.9 MIDDLEWARE - CORE SERVICES

LinkSmart middleware services provide a mean to register and discover devices and services in a LinkSmart eco-system. Integration of smart sensors, depth sensors and localization manager with LinkSmart is done by implementing Resource and Service Catalog APIs by Device Managers. Documentation, functional specification and also a Java SDK of the APIs assist the use case components for smooth device integration. Device Managers are registered into resource catalogue with a Registration document that describe the device and protocols being used for communication.

Table 19: Information of the Status and the required input of the middleware core services

Status
Recently LinkSmart has gone through major architectural and design changes. An initial version of the LinkSmart middleware with support of standard and lightweight protocols has been released and ready to be used by Satisfactory components. Resource and Catalog APIs have been extended based on the feedback from partners. A persistence layer for both catalog services has been implemented and now catalog entries are persisted and available upon next start. An initial design for authentication and authorization layer has been finalized and implementation will be ready before M30.
Required input
It has no dependency on other use-case components.

Results of Operation

LinkSmart middleware has already been deployed at the pilot site and its response/operation has been tested/used by the other components and all the tests were successful.

3.10 MIDDLEWARE - EVENT MANAGER

It supports publish-subscribe based messaging pattern through lightweight MQTT protocol. It is a central message broker that supports communication between Device Managers and high level services/components taking part in this business scenario. Upon registration into resource catalogue, device managers configure the topics on which data is being published. Therefore, services are required to learn the designated topics from resource catalogue.

Table 20: Information of the Status and the required input of the Event Manager

Status
Event Manager supporting MQTT protocol version 3.1 is available. Currently deployed Event Manager has been compiled with web-socket support.
Required input

LinkSmart core services need to be up and running. It is register as a broker service in a Service Catalogue.

Results of Operation

Event Manager has also been deployed at the pilot site and its response/operation has been tested/used by the other components with success.

3.11 MIDDLEWARE - EVENT AGGREGATOR

Many use-case components like automation system, sensors network and localization manager would like to store events and notifications in a CIDEM repository. Components like iDSS and Semantic Context Manager process this store data to extract and establish useful information. Event Aggregator resides on the LinkSmart side and subscribes to the Event Broker to get notified of the events being published by these components and later store these events in a CIDEM repository. All events/notifications are supposed to be CIDEM compliant.

Table 21: Information of the Status and the required input of the Event Aggregator

Status:
An updated instance based on current Catalog APIs version is ready that continuously monitors the Catalog services for life-cycle of device registrations and maintain corresponding subscriptions with Event Manager for data archive.
Required Input:
LinkSmart core services need to be up and running. CIDEM repository service is also available.

Results of Operation

It has been deployed at the pilot site and its response/operation has been tested/used by the other components. The reports of the tests were good and the operation is normal and continuous.

4 BSC-5.1 - REPAIR OR RESTORE AN ELECTROMECHANICAL MALFUNCTION

The goal of chapter 4 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-5.1.

Application Scenario BSC-5.1 is about corrective actions that need immediate attention. There exist various possible malfunctions during the normal operation of a pilot plant. Some of them can be treated after the current operation is completed while others need immediate attention in order for the pilot plant to continue the schedule actions. An electromechanical malfunction needs immediate care to avoid safety issues as well. This Application Scenario describes all the necessary actions in order to repair this kind of malfunctions and continue the normal operation of a pilot plant.

Goals:

- Perform work to repair or replace a faulty or degraded equipment

Objectives

- Reduce the time to respond to a malfunction
- Automatically provide appropriate information for the evaluation of the fault and the necessary actions to be applied by the involved actors

Figure 19: General information flow and sequence of activities of BSC-5.1

There are various possible malfunctions during the normal operation of a pilot plant. One of them could be an electromechanical malfunction which needs immediate care in order not to interrupt the normal operation of the pilot plant and to avoid safety issues as well. Possible malfunctions are burned out fuses, burned out resistors and malfunctioning solid state relays. AR tools, the iDSS and

the Content Management tools could help the technician to isolate the malfunction and repair or replace the faulty equipment with minimum or no downtime of the operation of the Pilot Plant and not losing any data of the ongoing experiment continuing as if the problem not occurred at all.

At each heating zone of the reactor there is a signal for the temperature and the controller. The process operator inserts the desired temperature set-point and a conventional PI controller is used to read the desired level of operation and to maintain the temperature at the specific set-point. When a malfunction occurs at a heating zone of the reactor then the automation technician examines 2 main cases in order to determine the cause of the problem. The process operator monitors the process through the HMI of the automation system. In case an abnormal situation occurs, he provides the initial notification to the technical team.

- **Case 1:** The process operator observes that the temperature has a large undershoot against the desired set-point of operation while the controller output is 100%.
- **Case 2:** The process operator observes that the temperature has a large overshoot against the desired set-point of operation while the controller output is 0%.

Preconditions:

- Existing of faulty or degraded equipment
- The SCADA system gives an alarm of abnormal behavior of a thermocouple
- All the thermocouples of the pilot plant is correctly mounted

Materials involved:

- Fuse
- Solid State Relay
- Terminals
- Resistor
- Multimeter
- Wires

Table 22: Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the BSC-5.1

1) The operator or the SCADA system identifies a malfunction
2) The operator declares the new job at the iDSS
3) The technician receives the ticket for the new job and moves to the point that the system has identified
4) The technician opens the door of the electrical enclosure
5) The AR tool (e.g. tablet) displays the appropriate electrical drawings to the technician
6) The AR tool indicates the involved fuse, screw terminals and solid state relay on a photo of the panel and magnifies on them at the schematics
7) If there is a hihi alarm the technician checks the solid state relay. If not go to step 14
8) After that the technician removes the appropriate fuse
9) The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system
10) The technician removes the wires of the relay and replaces it
11) The technician connects back the fuse
12) The operator starts the auto function of the controller

13) The operator gives feedback whether the problem has been solved or not
14) If there is a lolo alarm the technician removes the appropriate fuse and checks it with the multimeter
15) The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system
16) If the fuse is burned out, the technician replaces it
17) The AR tool indicates where the resistor is located on a photo of the panel
18) The technician removes the wires of the resistor from the terminals
19) The technician measures the resistor with the multimeter
20) If the resistor is burned out the technician replaces it
21) If not he connects back the fuse and the resistor wires
22) The technician takes a snapshot of the area where the equipment is placed and the AR tool displays a list with all the parts that exist at that point (from the identified assets as described at P&ID)
23) The technician choses the equipment that was involved along with the actions taken and the results
24) The AR tool sends feedback to the iDSS for the specific job (which was declared at step 2.

The next figure is showing the electrical cabinet of the pilot plant of BSC-5.1. The malfunction that is described at the scenario happens at a part that is mounted inside this cabinet

Figure 20 Electrical cabinet at of a pilot plant at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI

4.1 *SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED*

For the implementation of the BSC-5.1 a set of components of the Satisfactory platform are used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 21 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during T5.3.

Figure 21: Visualization of the utilized components of the SatisFactory Architecture at BSC-5.1

Table 23 presents the components that are common at BSC-5.1. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 23: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-5.1

Responsible partner	
CERTH	<p>Component: Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)</p> <p>Restrictions: The PDEC must have a continuous operation because pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor are on 24 hours.</p> <p>Prerequisites: OPC connection between the SCADA systems and the PDEC</p>
ISMB	<p>Component: Middleware – Device Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: Device manager is involved in the case of usage of some environmental data acquisition device. It should be technically possible to integrate involved devices through the device manager</p> <p>Prerequisites: Involved devices API and usage manual availability</p>
ISMB	<p>Component: Context-Aware Manager – Multiple Media Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: Only video distribution is provided by this component with deferred video distributed in case of incident</p>
ABE	<p>Component: Integrated DSS</p> <p>Restrictions: The malfunction must be identified outside of Integrated DSS and the notification must be fed to the DSS core</p>

	<p>Prerequisites: Availability of analytical maintenance procedures from the shop floors</p>
CERTH	<p>Component: Human resources workload balancing</p> <p>Restrictions: Possible lower efficiency for uncommon tasks</p> <p>Prerequisites: Available historical information about task assignments for optimal performance</p>
REGOLA	<p>Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools</p> <p>Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves</p>
REGOLA	<p>Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job</p> <p>Restrictions: The identification of the malfunction + notification of it + selection of maintenance procedure must be made by a higher level system. The presentation tools instead will present information about process conditions from this higher system and will interactively visualize the selected maintenance procedure to support actors to solve the fault</p> <p>Prerequisites: Formalized maintenance operating procedures to solve the fault. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves</p>
REGOLA	<p>Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework</p> <p>Restrictions: The Simulated Framework will be used to test the maintenance procedure only</p> <p>Prerequisites: Formalized maintenance operating procedures to solve the fault. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves</p>
GlassUP	<p>Component: Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI</p> <p>Restrictions: Glasses both to show repair instructions to the user, and to send images / video of the issues to the manager.</p>

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

4.1.1 Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC

This software component supports the transmission and transformation of the shop floor data to ISA-95 complaint format. It combines diverse data from shop-floor automation systems and the IoT sensors to support decision making, in events related to production activities, in smart factory incidents, etc. It can be promoted in two stages.

First, as a component of the automation system at in-house process systems. Secondly, it can be provided as a service to companies that already have process systems. The PDEC collects all the useful information of the Pilot Plants that are involved in SatisFactory and distributes them to other components (like Linksmart, CIDEM, etc.) through web services according to ISA-95. The PDEC translates OPC data to B2MML format and makes them available through RESTful services.

Figure 22: Overview window of the user interface of the PDEC

PDEC has various information about the connection and the communication of the automation system of the shop floor with the SatisFactory components. The above figure shows the Overview window of the interface of the component. The status of all the pilot plants at the shop floor, the communication methods that are used and the sampling setting can be seen at this window. Exploring to the other tabs, the user is able to see details about the data that are being sent from the automation system to the other components.

Table 24: Information of the Status and the required input of the PDEC

Status
The development and testing of the PDEC is completed and the software has been installed at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. The product is now finalized. There have been many tests and reconfigurations in order to be more effective and compliant with the other components of SatisFactory. At M16 the component started the nominal and continuous operation at the shop floor, sending data to the other components that have been installed at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. Since then, it has been working without any malfunctions or errors.
Required input
The inputs of PDEC are the data of the pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. It also receives feedback from the other components, according to the needs of each business scenario.

Results of operation

The component has proved that it is very stable and needs no much attention after the setup. It has been equipped with many functions which hadn't been planned at the beginning of the project. But, since the component can integrate data from different sources, convert them to useful information and transmit them to other components of SatisFactory, it is a valuable component and has a very important role at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI.

4.1.2 Context-Aware Manager – Multiple Media Manager

The Multiple Media Manager is a component responsible for distributing media from the shop floor to SatisFactory components. It is also responsible for handling and signaling WebRTC protocol to connect shop-floor location.

Table 25: Information of the Status and the required input of the Multiple Media manager

Status
<p>Current status is the Multiple Media Manager acquires the video from the smart assembly station using the same acquisition hardware of the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager and distributes it using MotionJPEG encoding. Also a deferred video feature is available in case of incident in order to be able to visualize the incident that has occurred from a remote location.</p> <p>WebRTC audio communication between Digital Andon St and Re-Adaptation Toolkit has been integrated in the current version. More stability and performance tests are required.</p>
Required input
<p>The Multiple Media Manager module requires a configuration file that will be stored in the CIDEM during the startup process and events received through LinkSmart Middleware.</p>

Results of Operation

The first set of features has been deployed at CERTH/CPERI at M17. Integration of the WebRTC communication and signaling has been performed at M20.

4.1.3 Integrated DSS

The Integrated DSS (iDSS) within the SatisFactory architecture (as described in D2.1 in M8) is a complex tool comprised by 5 sub-components, namely: DSS-Core, Maintenance Toolkit, Shop floor Feedback Engine, Incident Management Tools, Visual and Real-time Analytics Module. It also interacts with other components in order to carry out a specific task. The next figure shows the web-based UI of the iDSS component.

Figure 23: The web interface of the iDSS

In this scenario, it is envisaged that the following sub-components will be used: DSS-Core, Maintenance Procedures, Shop floor Feedback Engine, Incident Management Tools, Maintenance Toolkit, Real-time Analytics and maybe Visual Analytics Module. The main component is the DSS Core, which is responsible for orchestrating all the rest of the subcomponents, for ensuring that the output of each subcomponent is using the right channel and the appropriate format in order to be directed to external components and that external components can subscribe and be actually notified by the various events raised from iDSS subcomponents. The mobile UI of the component is being shown at the following figure. The first instance shows the first screen of the application, which is the logo of the SatisFactory project and the login view.

Figure 24: SatisFactory Shop floor Feedback Engine login view

The next views show how the successful completion of a task appears, including the date and time. There is also a screenshot of an uncompleted task, which is already in progress.

Figure 25: Two instances of the mobile UI of iDSS

The iDSS within BSC-5.1 receives a notification of an alarm by the automation system. The information on the generated incident is fed to the Incident Management Tools and it triggers the DSS Core to interact with the Maintenance Toolkit. Thus, the system is able to provide suggestions on the responsive actions required, along with the information necessary, which reside in the Repository. The information is combined and it will be redirected for visualization to the Shop Floor Feedback Engine and other visualization sub-components if necessary. Both UIs of the iDSS (web-based and mobile) have been tested for a significant period.

Certain functionalities to facilitate use have been further developed, taking into consideration remarks from the users, in order to increase the usability and effectiveness of the component, as well as the user's experience and satisfaction. In the figure below, the worker tries to start a task before choosing one and, thus, he/she receives a notification.

Figure 26: Notification of a task and the list of assets

The notification came on the screen because the user tried to do something out of the time order. The second screenshot of the mobile application shows the assets used in a shop floor. All assets exist in the application and are ready to be used. When a worker starts the implementation of a task he/she receives the steps of the SOP that need to be followed, in order to complete it. Moreover, for each step, where applicable, the worker also receives additional information, such as the schematics.

Figure 27: A view of the mobile app that shows the asset's schematics

Table 26: Information of the Status and the required input of the iDSS

Status
The development of the sub-components of the iDSS has been completed, in terms of the parts necessary to be tested at the Industry Lab. The focus has been in the DSS-Core, Shopfloor Feedback Engine and Incident Management Tools.
Required input
For iDSS to operate in BSC-5.1 the malfunction must be identified outside of Integrated DSS and the notification must be fed to the DSS core from the automation system and/or the smart sensor network in near real-time. Moreover, the analytical maintenance procedures and response strategies need to be made available from the shop floor involved and the related material and information to be made available at the Repository. Additionally, inferred ontologies from the Ontology Manager need to be available for inquiring.

Results of Operation

The iDSS subcomponent has been delivered to CERTH/CPERI.

4.1.4 Human Resources Workload Balancing

Human resources departments of industries always struggle in order to schedule and assign tasks to workers, mainly due to lack of available resources (i.e. a worker missing a particular day, a machine is unavailable due to other use or malfunction etc.). Usually, tasks are assigned at the beginning of each work day and this schedule should be followed throughout the day. The HR workload balancing toolkit provides an automated way to schedule work tasks and it schedules the tasks in order to achieve maximum gain. Each task is assigned to one or more workers, according to different criteria which apply for the task. The toolkit finds the most suitable solution for every type of task and creates the daily schedule.

Though automation through the toolkit is an improvement to the overall scheduling process, there are always exemptions, which should be dealt with. The most common deviations from the schedule happen when there is a machine malfunction and production cannot continue without first fixing the problem. Sometimes, there is also worker or raw material unavailability that appears and schedule should change because of these factors. For these cases, scheduling should change and adapt to the new conditions. Another important case in which scheduling should be readapted is when new tasks arrive during the work day and they should be scheduled and executed. The new imbedded tasks create the need for the readaptation of scheduling.

Figure 28: Scheduling work tasks and assignment to workers

Table 27: Information of the Status and the required input of the Human Resources Workload Balancing Toolkit

Status
The HR toolkit is available and the schedule is redirected to the Readaptation toolkit, so that it can be

displayed also there, if the manager/supervisor wishes to.

Required input

Information on the pending tasks in the beginning of the day and on the calculation of their criticality and other parameters. Information on the occurrence of un-programmed tasks occurring after the initial scheduling has been prepared.

Results of Operation

The first version of the HR toolkit was available in August 2016 (M20) and the final one for the implementation at CPERI was delivered in December 2016 (M24).

4.1.4.1 **Branch and Bound Algorithm**

Branch and Bound algorithm (B&B) is an exact method for finding an optimal solution to an NP-hard problem. It is an enumerative technique that can be applied to a wide class of combinatorial optimisation problems.

To describe the B&B algorithm, consider a case example described in the following table. The gain function for each job is determined by the weighted sum for a selected set of features (e.g. Asset Criticality, Task Criticality). The cost function for each job is determined by the duration or other selected feature for each one. The problem to determine the maximum outcome is NP-hard, i.e., it is unlikely that a polynomial-time algorithm can be developed for finding an optimal schedule.

The input data for the instance with n=4 jobs is given by the following table:

Table 28: Case Example

Jobs	1	2	3	4
P _j (gain)	12	8	15	9
D _j (cost)	16	26	25	27

A schedule corresponds to an assignment of jobs to the four positions in the job sequence.

Initialisation: To generate a schedule the starting point is no job sequenced and this is indicated by (*, *, *, *). Here "*" in the job sequence indicates that no job has yet been assigned to that position.

Step 1: To construct a schedule starting from the first position, we move from node (*, *, *, *) to one of the four possible nodes (1, *, *, *); (2, *, *, *); (3, *, *, *); (4, *, *, *).

Step 2: To assign the second job in the sequence, we branch from the each of these four nodes to three possibilities: branching from (1, *, *, *) gives (1, 2, *, *), (1, 3, *, *), and (1, 4, *, *); branching from (2, *, *, *) gives three possibilities (2, 1, *, *), (2, 3, *, *), and (2, 4, *, *), etc.

Step 3: Assigning the job to be processed in the third position immediately fixes the last job.

This process is represented by a branching tree. Each node of a tree corresponds to a partial schedule with several jobs assigned to the first positions and the remaining jobs unassigned.

Sequencing the unscheduled jobs in the SPT order and replacing their original due dates v_{jd} by a large artificial due date d is done temporarily in order to determine the Lower Bound for the current partial schedule. The resulting branch-and-bound tree is represented in the following figure. An example of calculating the lower bounds is given below.

Figure 29: Decision Tree based on Branch and Bound algorithm

The B&B algorithm has certain advantages and disadvantages.

Advantages of Branch & Bound algorithm: Finds an optimal solution (if the problem is of limited size and enumeration can be done in reasonable time).

Disadvantages of Branch & Bound algorithm: Time-consuming; the number of nodes in a branching tree can be too large. The algorithm finds the first complete schedule and then tries to improve it. Often developing the “promising” branches may lead to a large number of branches and leaves that finally may not provide an improvement. Thus, the size of the tree may grow exponentially without improving the best solution obtained. Careful planning of the tree can alleviate this disadvantage.

4.1.4.2 Initial Scheduling

iDSS is a system that helps enterprises in the decision making process. One part of that process is the time scheduling of tasks that should occur during the work day. The HR workload balancing toolkit consists on one part of the automatic creation of the initial daily schedule. This schedule is created and then it can be shown in other SatisFactory components such as the iDSS or the Re-adaptation toolkit, according with the production and the necessary needs of the company each day. Based on the Branch & Bound algorithm, Initial Scheduling assigns tasks to workers depending on availability, necessity, importance, and criticality.

The system allows different criteria for the tasks to be scheduled and there are a lot of conditions to be taken into consideration. Depending on the work plan, the working hours should be determined. Each company has different working hours. There are eight hour shifts, part – time shifts with a duration of four hour and special shifts with different working hours that should be considered for a schedule to be prepared. Another condition that should be considered is the absence of workers at a certain day. Workers may be absent due to a leave or because they are sick and call the company. Workers’ availability is also affected by the working shifts. Some workers are not present during the day because they have evening or night shifts. Furthermore, some tasks should be done only in certain shifts, eg. cleaning the shop floor must be done when the evening shift is over etc. Workers of different specialties may work only in the morning shift, such as engineers and IT technicians, but

there are factory workers who may work in all shifts. Finally, an important condition which is considered is whether or not the task can be completed from the enterprise's workers or there are need for an external collaborator/supplier.

Figure 30: Initial Schedule View – iDSS

Each task is scored according to criteria, based on criticality. Tasks and assets have different scores for their criticality and are accordingly classified. The default criteria can be configured in the system and applied, as show below. Assignments are made based on the workers' suitability and derive from the Maintenance Toolkit (trade) and inferred from Ontology framework (experience level).

Figure 31: Task and Asset Criticality Criteria

Figure 32: Worker Assignment

When a task is appointed to a worker a new field is created in the calendar. The time period needed for the task can be fixed or inferred, and this piece of information is also mentioned to the new field. A yellow box with the task id and the asset is the graphical notification. The assigned worker is shown in the list, marked green and a link with the task's element is also created. The scheduled task is then published to CIDEM.

Figure 33: Assignment of a Task to a Worker

4.1.4.3 Work Schedule Re –Adaptation

When a new task has to be scheduled in the work day, the readaptation of the work schedule is necessary. This part of the toolkit has a lot of potential for commercial use. It is needed in every work floor and independently of the enterprise’s size, because there are a lot of un-programmed and unscheduled tasks that arise and need to be performed. These inferred tasks must be dealt with and the main purpose of the HR toolkit is to readapt the work schedule in the most efficient way, to succeed in programming the tasks. Another purpose is to predict as accurately as possible those un-programmed tasks and inform in advance, so that they can be scheduled in the proper order. When an inferred task is arranged, a message is published to CIDEM with the new and old tasks in the desired order.

The HR workload balancing and re-adaptation engine is a sub-component of the iDSS which is responsible for monitoring the shop floor’s work schedule and the task list of each employee and optimizing the allocation of tasks to employees to improve the management of human resources. It operates in real-time and is able to schedule an arriving task by determining the starting time of the task, and allocate the most suitable employees to perform the arriving task based on their experience, current workload, impact on shop floor operation and other factors. Already scheduled tasks, can be re-scheduled automatically to be performed at another time in case they are affected from the insertion of the new task to the work schedule.

Table 29: Re - Adaptation Procedure

1) After the creation of the initial work schedule and the assignment of tasks, a new task is coming in for scheduling and execution
2) The new task is evaluated according to the criteria
3) The system assigns the task to a worker
4) The worker takes on the task
5) If the new task has higher priority, than the already executed task, the worker should stop the first task and start the new one
6) When the new one task is finished, the worker can assume the previous task to finish
7) If the new task has lower priority, than the already executed task, the worker finished their task and then assumes the new one
8) New tasks come in the system constantly and all should be discovered the same way
9) Re – adaptation of the work schedule is constant and AIMMS tries to achieve it in the most suitable and profitable way
10) The iDSS then is capable to notify all the other components of the Satisfactory platform for the re – adaptation of the schedule

An example of a work schedule at CPERI in XML format is shown below.

```
<WorkSchedule>
  <ID>1</ID>
  <Description>Current work schedule</Description>
  <PublishedDate>2016-08-03T16:05:17.5864066Z</PublishedDate>
  <WorkRequest>
    <ID>1111</ID>
```



```
<StartTime>2016-08-03T08:00:00</StartTime>
<EndTime>2016-08-03T17:00:00</EndTime>
<JobOrders>
  <JobOrder>
    <ID>112118</ID>
    <Description>Burned resistance JE201 on the injector.</Description>
    <StartTime>2016-08-03T09:00:00</StartTime>
    <EndTime>2016-08-03T09:30:00</EndTime>
    <Priority>1</Priority>
    <PersonnelRequirement>
      <PersonID>11</PersonID>
      <Description>personel1</Description>
    </PersonnelRequirement>
    <PhysicalAssetRequirement>
      <Description>asset1</Description>
    </PhysicalAssetRequirement>
    <MaterialRequirement>
      <Description>material1</Description>
    </MaterialRequirement>
  </JobOrder>
  <JobOrder>
    <ID>112115</ID>
    <Description>Broken trim-H on PCV502.</Description>
    <StartTime>2016-08-03T09:30:00</StartTime>
    <EndTime>2016-08-03T10:00:00</EndTime>
    <Priority>2</Priority>
    <PersonnelRequirement>
      <PersonID>12</PersonID>
      <Description>personel2</Description>
    </PersonnelRequirement>
    <PhysicalAssetRequirement>
      <Description>asset2</Description>
    </PhysicalAssetRequirement>
    <MaterialRequirement>
      <Description>material2</Description>
    </MaterialRequirement>
  </JobOrder>
</JobOrders>
```



```
<ID>112106</ID>
<Description>Replace Furnace R701 ./</Description>
<StartTime>2016-08-03T10:30:00</StartTime>
<EndTime>2016-08-03T13:00:00</EndTime>
<Priority>3</Priority>
<PersonnelRequirement>
  <PersonID>12</PersonID>
  <Description>personel3</Description>
</PersonnelRequirement>
<PhysicalAssetRequirement>
  <Description>asset3</Description>
</PhysicalAssetRequirement>
<MaterialRequirement>
  <Description>material3</Description>
</MaterialRequirement>
</JobOrder>
</JobOrders>
</WorkRequest>
</WorkSchedule>
```

At the pilot plant of CPERI, many tasks need the worker to be a chemical engineer. The tasks are appointed by the Initial Scheduling for the day. There are days when a chemical engineer task arises even if this was not previously known. This would mean that one of the chemical engineers working at CPERI needs to interrupt his/her scheduled task, to service the new task which has higher priority. The task the chemical engineer was previously working is pushed back and waits for the new one to be completed. The HR toolkit should be able to distinguish the different tasks with different priorities and assist in a way that all tasks are completed in the most effective way, because if there are too many interruptions, the tasks with the lowest priorities would remain unresolved for long time periods.

Figure 34: Re - Adaptation of Work Scheduling

Through the use of the real-time HR workload balancing and re-adaptation engine, the high priority maintenance task of the electromechanical malfunction is scheduled automatically to be performed as soon as possible and the appropriate workers who will perform the task are selected. As a result, the response time required to respond to the malfunction is reduced. According to the computed priority of the new task, the starting time of the task is set and the most suitable worker is assigned by taking into account the workload and the current status. The cost that is introduced by the insertion of the new task is also taken into account in order to select a solution which minimizes possible disruption that is caused to the already scheduled tasks. For evaluating the suitability of each worker given the type of a new task, historical task assignment data were utilized as well. Based on these data, a probabilistic model was created per each worker. Furthermore, semantically enriched information about the suitability of each worker given the type of a task is retrieved from the ontology manager. As a result, a suitability score is computed and taken into account when selecting a worker.

The process of the automated scheduling of an arriving task is described next. A new maintenance task of high priority, which has to be performed immediately, has been created. Attributes describing the task, such as the type of the task, estimated duration, priority weight and personnel requirements are defined and are passed to the HR work balancing and re-adaptation engine. The engine retrieves the current work schedule and creates the task lists per each worker. Then, based on the requirements of the new task and the rule-based hard constraints applied, a set of candidate workers who can perform the task is defined. The starting time of the new task along with the worker(s) who will perform the task are determined based on cost minimization in terms of employee capability and impact on the shop floor's work schedule. The new task is then added to the work schedule which is updated if necessary by re-setting the starting time of already scheduled tasks, and it is published to LinkSmart middleware.

A Graphical User Interface, which is shown in the following figure, is available in order to monitor the current status and possible changes that have been occurred in the work schedule.

Figure 35: Human Resources Workload Balancing and Job Assignment

An example applied at CPERI shop floor which demonstrates the operation described above, is the following: A new task of high priority with estimated duration of 1 hour arrived at 09:45. An Automation technician must be assigned to perform the new task. Two Automation technicians (ID:14, ID: 18) were candidates to perform the task. A 3-hour task with starting time at 09:30 was pre-assigned to technician 18. Technician 14 had also a 3-hour task starting at 10:30, along with a 30-minute task starting at 14:30. When the new task arrived, technician 18 was performing his task that was started 15 minutes ago, while technician 14 was idle but had his scheduled task starting at 10:30 which overlapped with the arriving task. The engine assigned the arriving task to worker 14 due to the lower adaptation cost (no running task had to be suspended). The arriving task started immediately because of its higher priority, and the pre-scheduled overlapping task of lower priority was finally rescheduled to be performed right after the arriving task. The updated work schedule containing the necessary changes was displayed on the IDSS UI.

4.1.4.4 **Work Schedule Publication**

The publication of the work schedule to the other components is achieved through CIDEM and the middleware. Firstly, the initial set up of procedures is made on CIDEM, then there is the Human Resources automated scheduling and finally the schedule's publication through LinkSmart to CIDEM. The publication process is shown at the table below.

Table 30: Work Schedule Publication

Step 1: Initial set – up of procedures on CIDEM
Step 2: Human Resources automated scheduling
Step 2: Publication of scheduling through LinkSmart to CIDEM

4.1.5 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools

The AR SOP Creation Tool is the application that will be used in the factory context to define and edit the procedure in order to show it by means of the AR Visualization Tool.

The AR Creation Tool is based on two modules:

- The resource module
- The operating procedure module.

The **resource module** allows for the creation of a resource repository that can be used by any procedure. It allows the resource definition, supporting as resources: images, video, 3d models, documents and so on.

The **Operating procedure module** allows for the definition of a procedure in terms of its own steps, namely:

- Operations
- Phases
- Actions
- The relationships connecting them.

A complete procedure definition will produce as output a graph enabling the procedure execution according to a well-defined navigation model.

To support the procedure definition, the AR Creation Tool makes available an inventory allowing the definition of all the elements required to execute the procedure.

Each element in the procedure (operation, phase, action, relationship) may be described in terms of its own base elements. The maximum possible level of detail is in the Action, featuring a Descriptive Layer.

The Descriptive Layer make possible to describe each action with different contents:

- simple text
- images
- videos
- 3d models.

Please, note, it is not mandatory to insert all the possible Descriptive Layers for each single action; only those related to a specific content to be used to describe the Action are required.

It is possible to define the list of the objects required to execute the action getting them from the inventory already filled by means of elements such: Components, Equipment and Tools.

The sequence of the Actions to be executed is produced by the Relationships due to the fact that, in facts, the Relationships define an ordering along the Action sequences. They are:

- Consecutive
- Undefined
- Conditional
- Repeated
- Other.

The procedure defined so far could be exported as a bundle to be saved in the repository of the Operative Procedures or Maintenance Procedures.

Table 31: Information of the Status and the required input of the AR SOP Creation Tool

Status
The AR SOP Creation Tool development is completed and the application has been extensively tested.
Required input
The data required as input for the AR SOP Creation Tool is the operating procedure description and all types of content able to provide a detailed and complete description of it. This information must be provided by CERTH .

Results of operations

The Creation Tool has undergone to extensive testing. Some minor bugs have been identified and corrected. The Package To Bundle application has been optimized in order to further automate the process needed to deploy the SOP Bundle on the different platforms. Furthermore, the Creation Tool is under a cycle of tests in the COMAU Shop Floor, where the employees have installed the AR Platform and are creating and editing procedures autonomously.

About BSC.5-1.

In BSC-5.1 the AR OP Creation Tool was used to define the resources and the inventory required by the procedure (images, videos, etc.) according to the procedure definition along the steps 3-24 in terms of Operations, Phases, Actions and Relationships. Due to the nature of the Scenario, no 3D AR resources were identified and the Presentation Tool provides stepwise information using images, videos and documents.

Figure 36: Deployment of the AR SOP Creation Tool at CPERI

4.1.6 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job

The AR Presentation Tool is the software able to navigate the bundle that is the output of the Creation Tool. It has the capability of navigate the procedure step by step, following sequences, loops and conditions included in the procedure and, in doing this, it delivers the content which has been previously managed and included as resource by the Creation Tool.

The content delivered could depend on the capabilities of the platform, so, for example, the operator will be exposed to video, sound, images, 3D models etc. depending on the fact that h/w platform can render that kind of content. Furthermore, the operator has the opportunity to choose the best content that fit its own needs within the contents that can be deployed and delivered in the platform he/she is actually using.

In this model, the AR content is one of several content types that can be made available in the AR Presentation Tool; it can be triggered in the following different ways:

- marker based; i.e., by means of the recognition of a high contrast, traditional markers that provide the anchor to which the AR content is bound
- Feature based; i.e., by means of the recognition of a general image featuring enough complexity to be uniquely identified, so providing the anchor to which the AR content is bound.

The Presentation Tool could be deployed on several platforms, being able, as told, to adapt the content presented to the operator to its own capabilities.

Table 32: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The deployment of the AR SOP Presentation Tool at CPERI is completed. Some plugins are under further tests until M30.
Required input
A name that uniquely identifies the procedure to be performed.

Results of operations

The AR SOP Presentation Tool has undergone extensive testing. Some minor bugs have been identified and corrected. Further optimizations will continue until the end of T2.5 and T4.3 (M30).

Pending actions

The View Channel plugin has been developed and must be tested.

4.1.7 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework

The Presentation Tool could be used in a simulated framework. The immersion in the target environment is not required to:

- navigate the procedure step by step
- Be exposed to the content included in that step.

This simulation framework allows for review of the procedure and its contents, for learning, for testing, without the need for reality hooks able to trigger the AR content.

Table 33: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The deployment of the AR SOP Presentation Tool at CPERI is completed. Some plugins are under further tests until M30.
Required input
A name that uniquely identifies the procedure to be performed.

Results of Operation

The AR SOP Presentation Tool has undergone extensive testing. Some minor bugs have been identified and corrected. Further optimizations will continue until the end of T2.5 and T4.3 (M30).

4.1.8 Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI

Glassup devices are AR Glasses designed to be worn by shop floor workers, thus providing them with sensors, camera and a display to show relevant information about working environment and surroundings. In this scenario, the AR Glasses will show shop floor workers all required instructions in order to repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction. The worker will be able to navigate through the different steps of the repair procedure and to send the video taken from the on-board camera to senior workers asking for help.

Table 34: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status

The first prototype is completed and the thermal camera has been properly integrated with the Glasses. The firmware has been completed and the SDK now supports all the API calls that are now available. We are now reviewing the aesthetics and ergonomics of the Glasses and working for all the certifications required to launch our device to the market.

Figure 37: The 2nd version of the smart glasses

Required input

The required input for AR glasses is the maintenance procedure to be shown to the worker subdivided in the various steps and other useful information related to the topic. All information should come from the Repository and forwarded to the Glasses by specific mobile applications developed by Regola.

Results of operation

A fully functional AR Glasses has been sent to the shop floor to be tested in the operator’s workflow. The device has been fully integrated with the others components of SatisFactory, however a revised document on the API calls will be sent to eventually update the communication with the device.

4.2 SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED

The actors at SatisFactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-5.1.

Table 35: List with the SatisFactory actors’ groups that are involved at BSC-5.1

	Groups of actors
BSC 5.1	Maintenance manager
	Electrical technician
	Process technician
	Automation technician
	Process operator
	Process supervisor

4.3 STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 5.1

Business Scenario 5.1 will come as a great assistance to the workers of CERTH/CPERI regarding some of their procedures at the shop floor. There have been many tests and a detailed analysis during the design phase of each component in order to determine their usability and to increase the positive effect that they will have to the workers. The BSC-5.1 will increase the safety at the shop floor, will enhance the involved workers at the needed actions and contribute at their general satisfaction. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-5.1.

Table 36 : Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-5.1

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
BSC-5.1 – Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction												
Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Context-Aware Manager - Multimedia Manager	Design		Set-up		Deployment			Operation				
Integrated DSS	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation					
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools	Design		Set-up		Deployment			Operation				
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job	Design		Set-up		Deployment			Operation				
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework	Design		Set-up		Deployment			Operation				
Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses	Design			Set-up		Deployment		Operation				
GENERAL COMPONENTS												
Repository-Asset machinery production models	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation					
Operational platform with augmented intelligence	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation					
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation					
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools	Design			Set-up		Deployment		Operation				
Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools	Design			Set-up		Deployment		Operation				
Middleware – Device Manager	Design		Set-up			Deployment		Operation				
Middleware - Core Services	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation						
Middleware - Event Manager	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation						
Event Aggregator	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation					

5 BSC-5.2 – STARTUP PROCEDURES FOR PILOT PLANTS

The goal of chapter 5 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and initial usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-5.2. Business Scenario BSC-5.2 is about the critical start-up step of operating hydroprocessing pilot plants and involves the loading of the feed tank, as the first step of the overall experimental plan, which needs to be carefully performed to allow the optimal feedstock introduction in the downstream catalytic system. The proper feed tank loading is the result of starting the recycling pump and systematically heating the feed lines according to the specific feedstock quality characteristics and experimental run objectives set the process supervisor and implementing the loading strategy by the process technician. It is also important that feed tank loading follows the proper maintenance of the hydroprocessing plant, to allow technical problems during the future experimental run. This Application Scenario has as a goal to make sure that the proper steps will be followed even from workers with small experience.

Goals:

- Nominal startup of a pilot plant based on standard operating procedures
- Create a Standard Operating Procedure for starting/operating/shutdown a pilot plant

Objective:

- Reduce startup time
- Avoid errors during the startup procedures

The challenge is to create a standard procedure for starting up a pilot plant in order first to reduce startup time and second to avoid errors during the startup procedures increasing the safety and reducing stress. The final goal is to Startup the pilot plant with no errors or conflicts and with the least usage of recourses (time consumed, actors involved, materials and tools needed).

Preconditions:

- All lines, feed containers, reactor and separator system should be clean
- Reactor should be loaded with catalyst
- Successfully passed pressure test

Materials involved:

- Recycling pump P51A
- Feed container
- 3-way valve 5HV-52A
- Feed intake line
- Scale
- Pressure control valve PCV-51A
- Pressure indicator PI-53A
- Weight transmitter WT-51A
- Sample bottle

- Hood
- Glass door

Table 37: Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the BSC-5.2

1) Enable the pump interface by setting it ON from unit PC
2) Place container close to the recycling pump
3) Bring the feed intake line next to the recycling pump
4) Hood removal
5) Feed container shaking
6) Open feed container lid
7) Place the long side of the feed intake line on the feed container
8) Connect the other side of the feed intake line to the 3-way valve
9) Place the hood on top of the feed container
10) Open the glass door in front of the feed container
11) Press the zero button on the scale
12) Open the 3-way valve by turning it to be aligned with the feed intake line
13) Start the pump by pressing the ON/OFF button (if ON a green light will be displayed)
14) Open and close the 2HV valve until liquid flows
15) Loosen the PCV-51A
16) Observe on the WT-51 the gradual weight increase
17) Press the TIC-51A button to start the temperature increase in the feed container and the associated lines
18) Wait until the desired feed quantity is loaded
19) Switch off the 3-way valve opposing the direction of the feed intake line
20) Remove the feed intake line
21) Place feed container lid and close it
22) Remove feed container
23) Clean feed intake line
24) Store feed intake line
25) Close the glass door of the feed container
26) Bring the waste container
27) Open the lid of the waste container
28) Empty the glass bottle of the valve 2HV-54A outlet to the waste container
29) Close the lid of the waste container
30) Close the lid of the glass bottle we just emptied
31) Clean the 3-way valve inlet with paper
32) Store the waste container

Figure 38 VB01 hydro processing Pilot Plant at CETH/CPERI shop floor

5.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED

For the implementation of the BSC-5.2 a set of components of the SatisFactory platform will be used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 39 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during task T5.3.

Figure 39: Visualization of the utilized components of the SatisFactory Architecture at BSC-5.2

Table 38 presents the components that are common at BSC-5.2. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 38: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-5.2

Responsible partner	
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools
	Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job
	Restrictions: The presentation tools will be visualize all and only the supported contents (images, text, icons)
	Prerequisites: Clear and effective messages (images, text, icons) have to be generated at runtime by external

	specialized components and sent to AR Tools that will present these contents in pre-designed HMIs
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework
	Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
CERTH	Component: Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)
	Restrictions: The PDEC must have a continuous operation because pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor are on 24 hours.
	Prerequisites: OPC connection between the SCADA systems and the PDEC
GlassUP	Component: Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI
	Restrictions: Glasses used to display text and image instructions to user.
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager
	Restrictions: Safety equipment recognized if necessary and machine learning regained in advance. GCRM can detect pre-defined gestures
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon St
	Prerequisites: List of assembly procedure instructions (JPEG, PNG or PDF), list of maintenance or supervision mode instructions (JPEG, PNG or PDF)

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

5.1.1 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools

The AR SOP Creation Tool has been analyzed in detail at the paragraph 4.1.5. At the BSC-5.2, the AR SOP Creation Tool is used to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that will be created. This is a very helpful function which can help both experienced and novice employees.

5.1.2 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job

The AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.6 . For BSC-5.2 the resulting training scenario was presented using the Presentation tool using a tablet device.

Figure 40: Deployment of the AR SOP Presentation Tool at CPERI (BSC5.2)

5.1.3 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework

The AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.7. At the BSC-5.2, this component is used in combination with the AR Creation Tools and the AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that were created.

5.1.4 Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC

The Plant Data Exchange Component has been described with details at section 4.1.1 . The BSC-5.2 uses PDEC to check some variables of the involved pilot plant and it also receives feedback regarding the actions of the operators.

5.1.5 Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI

The Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices component is also being used at BSC-5.1 and it has been analyzed at paragraph 4.1.8 . The worker will wear the smart glasses and he/she will be able to receive useful information about the actions that have to be done.

5.1.6 Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager

The Gesture & Content Recognition Manager is a headless module that is deployed to the smart assembly stations and is in charge of:

- capture user gestures for browsing through assembly instructions (Figure 41)
- require maintenance assistance triggering specific events
- implement a fall detection system (Figure 42)
- signaling presence of workers in the nearby area
- signaling assembly progress updates
- detect safety equipment wear by workers on the smart assembly stations (Figure 44)

The following figure shows two gestures of a worker that can be recognized from the system. This way the worker would be able to give command to the platform remotely while he is working on something in the shop floor. The upper left image shows a “LeftHandSwipeRight” gesture that is recognized from the system and the lower left image presents the message that is displayed at the interface of the component when this gesture is recognized. The upper right image shows a “BothHandsRaised” gesture that is recognized from the system and the lower right image presents the message that is displayed at the interface of the component when the gesture is recognized.

Figure 41: Recognition of worker's gesture

Figure 42 shows a case of a fall of a worker that can be recognised from the component. Immediately after a detection of an incident, a message to the platform is being sent and all involved components will be notified.

Figure 42: Fall detection at CERTH/CPERI shop floor

Furthermore, an application has been developed in order to test the functionality and the behaviour of falling detection function. Figure 43 shows the messages that are displayed at the test application when the component detects a fall of a worker. These messages are also being sent to the Satisfactory platform in order to be used from all related components. This function focuses only to the station where the assembly and gesture related functionalities are provided to the workers. It increases the safety of the workers at the shop floor area and makes them feel more secure and confident.

Figure 43: Falling detection messages

The detection of safety equipment worn by workers is another function of the component as mentioned above. The safety equipment which can be detected are helmet and jacket. The next figure shows a fully equipped worker.

Figure 44: Fully equipped worker at CERTH/CPERI shop floor

The hardware that has been installed for this component is shown at the next two figures.

Figure 45: Kinect camera installed for the gesture component

Figure 46: NUC pc installed for the gesture component

Figure 45 shows the Kinect camera which captures the movements of the workers and Figure 46 shows the pc with the software of the component.

Table 39: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
All the listed features were deployed in the first version, aside for the last one that was refined to work on the target hardware platform in the second iteration.
Required input
The module requires gestures from the worker on the smart assembly station

Results of Operation

The first version has been deployed with the preliminary version at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor at M18. A new version enabling gestures to handle WebRTC calls has been deployed at CERTH/CPERI at M20.

5.1.7 Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon St Component

The Digital Andon St component is a component that acts as an enabler in order to facilitate performing specific operations through the visual representation of status information.

Figure 47: A screen shot of the Digital Andon St function

The first iteration of the Digital Andon St was deployed in the smart assembly stations and directly connected to the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager. The latter is a headless component that interacts directly with the Digital Andon St system. The goal is to provide the worker useful information while performing the assembly task. While browsing through the information is a direct responsibility of the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager component, the Digital Andon St is in charge of displaying gesture-related information and dispatch notifications about the progress status. Furthermore, the Digital Andon St allows operators to make or receive VOIP calls from their supervisors leveraging on Multiple Media Manager signaling services. Refinements, debugging and integration were the object of the second iteration of the development.

Table 40: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The Digital Andon St has been tested with other components such as the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager and the Toolkit for re-adaptation. The possibility to replace the assistance mode with a malfunction report to iDSS is still being considered and the decision will be made after the first iteration of deployment at Sunlight and Comau.
Required input

Gestures form the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager component, assembly instructions to be displayed.

Results of Operation

The first set of features has been deployed at CErTH/CPeRI at M17. Various refinements and integration of the WebRTC communication has been performed at M20.

5.2 SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED

The actors at SatisFactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-5.2.

Table 41: List with the SatisFactory actors' groups that are involved at BSC-5.2

BSC 5.2	Groups of actors
	Process operator
	Process supervisor
	Process technician
	Maintenance supervisor

5.3 STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 5.2

Business Scenario 5.2 is going to assist process operators and technicians in a standard procedure which includes the startup of a pilot plant. The operators will be enhanced by the actions of the scenario and they will be more confident about the procedures that they perform. There have been many tests and a detailed analysis during the design phase of each component in order to determine their usability and to increase the positive effect that they will have to the workers. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-5.2.

Table 42: Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-5.2

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
BSC-5.2 –Startup procedures for pilot plants												
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
GENERAL COMPONENTS												
Repository-Asset machinery production models	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Operational platform with augmented intelligence	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Middleware – Device Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Middleware - Core Services	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Middleware - Event Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								
Event Aggregator	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation								

6 BSC-5.3 – RECONFIGURATION OF PROCESS FLOW AND ACTIONS FOR FLEXIBLE REDESIGN OF PRODUCTION PROCEDURES

The goal of chapter 6 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and initial usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-5.3. This scenario of CERTH refers to the need to alter the operation of a pilot plant. A number of required actions need to be executed in order for the process configuration to be suitable for the new operation.

Goals:

- Improvement of process work flow for the reconfiguration of a multipurpose unit

Objectives:

- Provide alternatives based on predefined flows or past configurations
- Reduce the time needed for the pilot plant startup
- Avoid delays and failures during the reconfiguration between different workflow scenarios of a pilot plant

In this application scenario, since different gases are going to be used in the new operating conditions, the calibrated mass flow controllers along with the appropriate gas bottles need to be installed. Moreover, the automation system variables and alarm bounds have to be updated, while the method on the chromatograph also needs to be changed. Finally, the last action of the procedure before the pilot plant is ready to be used in the new operating conditions is to perform pressure tests using helium in order to detect possible leaks.

Alternatives based on:

- Input flows
- Input type of gases
- Combination of mixtures
- Input liquid products
- Operating ranges for temperature & pressure
- Reactor architecture

Basic Categories of performed actions:

- Install calibrated mass flow controllers (MFC)
- Install Appropriate gas bottles (GB)
- Update the automation system variables and alarm bound
- Change the method on the chromatograph
- Perform a pressure test

Preconditions:

- The operation of the pilot plant has finished and there is a need to start under different conditions. The SCADA system gives an alarm of abnormal behavior of a thermocouple

- Previous experiment: Methane steam reforming (0-5000cc/min CH₄, 5 barg, 500 °C, S/C = 3)
- Next experiment: Ethane steam reforming (0-3000 cc/min C₂H₆, 10 barg, 300 °C, S/C= 2)

Post conditions:

- **Success Guarantees:** Readaptation of production based on upcoming experiment needs
- **Failure end conditions:** Increment of the workflow complexity of the experiments

Materials involved:

- Mass Flow Controller (MFC) FV
- Mass Flow Controller (MFC) FV-21C
- Gas Bottles (GB)
- Gas Chromatograph
- Helium Leak Detector (HLD)

Table 43: Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the BSC-5.3

1)	Identify the MFC that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane, FT/FV-21C)
2)	The volumetric flow rate range required at the previous experiment is 0-5000 cc/min, while the next experiment is 0-3000 cc/min, thus another MFC, calibrated for Ethane, should be installed.
3)	Calibrate the new MFC according to the gas (ethane) and the flowrate (0-3000 cc/min) to be used (if needed)
4)	Uninstall the previous MFC and install the new MFC
5)	Identify the GB that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane)
6)	Make sure that the valve of the GB is closed
7)	Remove the previously used GB (methane)
8)	Install the new GB (ethane)
9)	Update the ranges of the installed MFC in the HMI Database. The new MFC's volumetric flow rate range is 0-3000 cc/min.
10)	Update the upper and lower boundaries of alarms in the HMI Database. Volumetric flow rate (0-3000 cc /min), pressure (0-10 bar) and temperature (0-300 °C) boundaries need to be updated.
11)	Change the method that is used in the chromatograph so that the new outlet stream's composition can be identified. The previous method is "SYNGAS22.M" while the new one to be used is "SYNEX21.M"
12)	After everything (MFC & GB) have been installed in the pilot plant a pressure test needs to be performed in order to check for possible leaks before operating the unit.
13)	In order to perform a pressure loss test Valves HV-81 (or HV-80) and 6HV-81 needs to be (manually) closed.
14)	Subsequently nitrogen is introduced into the system by setting the appropriate MFC's (FC-21C) volumetric flow rate at 200 cc/min.
15)	When the pressure at PI-81 reaches 10 bar (depending on the reaction's conditions), the flow rate is set to 0 cc/min and Valve XV-21C is closed.
16)	The pressure loss test is performed overnight, pressurizing by mean of Valve XV-21C and HV-81. If loss of pressure exceeds 5% overnight, or the leaking flow exceeds 2cc/min, then check for leaks with Helium Leak Detector (HLD)

Figure 48 SynGas Pilot Plant at CETH/CPERI shop floor

6.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED

For the implementation of the BSC-5.3 a set of components of the SatisFactory platform will be used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 49 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during T5.3. Each one of the components has a specific role which is described with details at this chapter.

Figure 49 Visualization of the utilized components of the SatisFactory Architecture at BSC-5.3

Table 44 presents the components that are common at BSC-5.3. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 44: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-5.3

Responsible partner	
ABE	Component: Integrated DSS
	Prerequisites: Provision of all necessary data from the shop floors. Working environment and scheduling allows for all needed maintenance procedures.
	Restrictions: In case all maintenance activities cannot be performed for some reason, information is needed on how to prioritise them.
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools
	Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job
	Restrictions: The presentation tools will be visualize all and only the supported contents (images, text, icons)
	Prerequisites: Clear and effective messages (images, text, icons) have to be generated at runtime by external specialized components and sent to AR Tools that will present these contents in pre-designed HMIs
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework
	Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
CERTH	Component: Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)
	Restrictions: The PDEC must have a continuous operation because pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor are on 24 hours.
	Prerequisites: OPC connection between the SCADA systems and the PDEC

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

6.1.1 Integrated DSS

As previously described, the iDSS interacts with other components in order to carry out a specific task. The iDSS within BSC-5.3 receives a notification of a need for reconfiguration most probably by an Actor. The DSS Core will be triggered to interact by the Incident Management Tool with the Maintenance Toolkit. Thus, the system is able to provide suggestions on the actions required, along with the information necessary, which reside in the Repository. The information is combined in the Shop floor Feedback Engine and it will be redirected to the corresponding visualization sub-component. More details about the iDSS are presented at paragraph 4.1.3.

Table 45: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
As previously stated, the first version of the development of the sub-components of the iDSS has

been delivered in August 2016 (M20), with the main focus being up to this point in the DSS-Core, Maintenance Toolkit. The second and last version for the CPERI premises was delivered in December 2016 (M24).

Required input

For iDSS to operate in BSC-5.3, the need for reconfiguration must be identified outside of Integrated DSS and the notification must be fed to the DSS core from the operator/actor. Moreover, the analytical response strategies need to be made available from the shop floor involved and the related material and information to be made available at the Repository. Additionally, inferred ontologies from the Ontology Manager need to be available for inquiring.

Results of Operation

The first version of the iDSS with the sub-components necessary for the implementation of this specific Business Scenario was ready by July 2016 (M19). Several parts of the tool were made gradually available from August 2016 (M20) until December 2016 (M24), in order to test the information flow applicability.

6.1.2 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools

The AR SOP Creation Tool has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.5 . At the BSC-5.3, the AR SOP Creation Tool is used to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that will be created. This is a very helpful function which can help both experienced and novice employees. The whole procedure of the reconfiguration of the process of the pilot plant will be demonstrated through the AR tools and will give extra assistance to the operators and the technicians who are involved at this business scenario.

6.1.3 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job

The AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.6. BSC-5.3 was fully modelled in the AR OP Creation Tool including AR 3D animations and the resulting training scenario was presented via the Presentation tool using a tablet device. This tool is responsible to present the created information to the workers through the AR tools.

6.1.4 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework

The AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.7. At the BSC-5.3, this component is used in combination with the AR Creation Tools and the AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that were created.

6.1.5 Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC

The Plant Data Exchange Component has been described with details at section 4.1.1 . The BSC-5.3 uses PDEC to validate the actions of the operators and the technicians during the reconfiguration of the process flow of the pilot plant.

6.2 SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED

The actors at SatisFactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-5.3.

Table 46: List with the SatisFactory actors' groups that are involved at BSC-5.3

	Groups of actors
BSC 5.3	Floor Manager
	Electrical technician
	Process technician
	Automation technician
	Process operator
	Process supervisor

6.3 STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 5.3

Business Scenario 5.3 will be a guide for the process operators and the technicians in order to perform the reconfiguration of the process flow at a pilot plant inside the shop floor of CErTH/CPERI. This procedure is very complex and frequently the workers are facing various difficulties. The components that have been decided to be involved in this scenario are focusing on the assistance of the workers and on how to make their actions easier and more accurate. Thus, the confidence of the workers is increasing along with their satisfaction. They are able to perform their work easier, facing fewer problems. This scenario is also used for training purposes on novice workers. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-5.3.

Table 47: Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-5.3

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	
BSC-5.3 –Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures													
Integrated DSS	Design	Set-up				Deployment				Operation			
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools	Design	Set-up				Deployment				Operation			
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job	Design	Set-up				Deployment				Operation			
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework	Design	Set-up				Deployment				Operation			
Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation							
GENERAL COMPONENTS													
Repository-Asset machinery, production models	Design	Set-up			Deployment					Operation			
Operational platform with augmented intelligence	Design	Set-up				Deployment				Operation			
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager	Design	Set-up			Deployment					Operation			
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment		Operation				
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up			Deployment		Operation			
Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up			Deployment		Operation			
Middleware – Device Manager	Design	Set-up				Deployment		Operation					
Middleware - Core Services	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation							
Middleware - Event Manager	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation							
Event Aggregator	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation							

7 BSC-6.1 – RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS AND PATH OPTIMIZATION FOR WORKERS MOVEMENT ON THE SHOP FLOOR

The goal of chapter 7 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and initial usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-6.1. The Business Scenario 6.1 of CERTH refers to movement at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. Two functions for this scenario have been implemented, one about recognition of incidents and one about the localization within the shop floor. Many incidents mostly minor but sometimes major with many workers involved, could happen every day in an industrial shop floor.

Goals:

- Prevent incidents by online monitoring of the status at the shop-floor
- Optimize movement at the shop floor

Objective

- Reduce incidents caused by accidental drop of objects or movement of materials through frequently used corridors concurrently by many workers
- Identify potential incidents of a worker

The purpose of this scenario is to reduce the number of this kind of incidents and to give optimal notification to workers moving inside the shop floor. This will have a positive impact to the workers' safety, which is a main aspect that SatisFactory targets.

Figure 50 Movement tracking at CERTH/CPERI's shop floor through normal camera

Figure 51 Movement tracking at CERTH/CPERI's shop floor through depth camera

Minor incidents involving workers frequently occur, causing delays and/or difficulties to complete the performed actions. Identification of such incidents and their severity, along with automatically recalling knowhow based on previously occurred incidents and providing suggested actions, would be a substantial solution to the problem. There are some areas of the shop floor that need particular attention from the workers when they are moving inside them. SatisFactory will be an assistant to the workers, trying to find optimal and safer paths for them to move and to perform their actions.

The safety of the workers is the main concept of this business scenario by providing the optimal way to perform standard procedures as well as optimal 3D movement within the shop floor.

7.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED

For the implementation of the BSC-6.1 a set of components of the SatisFactory platform will be used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 52 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during task T5.3.

Figure 52: Visualization of the utilized components of the SatisFactory Architecture at BSC-6.1

Table 48 presents the components that are common at BSC-6.1. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 48: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-6.1

Responsible partner	
ISMB	<p>Component: Smart Sensor Network - Dependable Network Infrastructure</p> <p>Restrictions: UWB radio connectivity can be affected by the harsh industrial environment</p> <p>Prerequisites: UWB anchor nodes and a gateway has to be deployed</p>
ISMB	<p>Component: Smart Sensor Network - UWB Localization Devices</p> <p>Restrictions: UWB radio connectivity can be affected by the harsh industrial environment</p> <p>Prerequisites: UWB anchor nodes and a gateway has to be deployed</p>

CERTH	Component: Smart Sensor Network - Depth Sensor Network
	Restrictions: There should NOT be materials that would probably lead to misfunctionality of the cameras (areas with a lot glasses, mirrors, and other reflection materials)
	Prerequisites: There should be available (a) the architectural map (floor plan) of the area under interest, (b) TCP/IP network, (c) power supply
CERTH	Component: Smart Sensor Network - Thermal Sensor Network
	Prerequisites: There should be available (a) TCP/IP network, (b) power supply.
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Localization Manager
	Prerequisites: Shop floor layout is available in electronic format (general user safety information are available)
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager
	Restrictions: If it's in scope of this UC to monitor if a worker is wearing the required safety equipment for the desired area, cameras needs to be placed in the specific positions with specific view angles. Moreover, fall detection system is in scope and active in the smart assembly areas.
CERTH	Component: Integrated DSS - Incident Management Tools
	Restrictions: It will be able to detect incidents only to the areas that are monitored by cameras (depth/thermal). The number of cameras is depended on the area under interest
	Prerequisites: The architectural map (floor plan) of the area under monitoring should be available, the material of the area should be appropriate (there are problems with areas with a lot glasses, mirrors, and other reflection materials)
GlassUP	Component: Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices - Glasses UI
	Restrictions: Glasses only to display alert signals to user.
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon St
	Prerequisites: Static assembly instructions must be available

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

7.1.1 Smart Sensor Network - Dependable Network Infrastructure

The dependable sensor network is a subset of the Smart Sensor Network (SSN) consisting of heterogeneous devices that allow the interaction between the physical world and the SatisFactory framework.

The dependable sensor network consists of heterogeneous devices that allow interaction between physical world and SatisFactory framework. These devices guarantee communication robustness in harsh industrial environments from the radio propagation point of view. The heterogenous devices are low power wireless sensor nodes which use multiple radio interfaces to perform the robust communication. The dependable network infrastructure hosts sensing and actuation applications which integrate shop floor events into the cyber-world following an IoT approach.

Table 49: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The multi-radio modules and RF interfaces have been designed. A first version of the system has been developed and tested with a single-radio node based on 6LoWPAN standard. The single-radio node uses channel hopping techniques to perform robust communication. The dependable network infrastructure based on multi-radio nodes is under development.
Required input
Communication and application requirements related to the sensors.

Results of operation

The dependable network infrastructure has been tested with one temperature sensor node based on the 6LoWPAN standard. The infrastructure provided robust communication to single-radio nodes by tracking compromised channels and indicating to the node the best channel to communicate. The system was integrated with the LinkSmart Catalog APIs “version 0.2.0” and distribution “version 0.2.0”.

7.1.2 Smart Sensor Network - UWB Localization Devices

The UWB Localization Devices can be of three types: tag, anchor and gateway. They are used to track workers enabling safety management in the shop-floor. Anchor nodes are deployed in fixed and well know positions in the working area. Tag nodes have unknown positions and are worn by workers. Each tag performs distance measurements with respect to the anchors by means of an incorporated UWB transceiver. Additionally, they use inertial sensors to track the kinematics of workers. A localization algorithm runs on the tag to estimate their position (i.e., position of worker). The position is estimated by using the collected ranging measurements and the measured kinematics. The gateway is the end-point of the Ultra Wide Band (UWB) based localization system. It receives the localization data from tags and forwards it to Localization Manager (described at section 7.1.6) through LinkSmart.

At the CERTH/CPERI shop floor, it is deployed a UWB-based localization system with four anchors, two tags, which are the UWB-based wearable devices, and one UWB gateway. Both anchor nodes and gateway are protected with a IP66 boxes.

The deployed anchor nodes are shown at the next table.

Table 50: Installed anchor nodes at CERTH/CPERI shop floor for the localization manager

Along with the above hardware, there is the Ultra Wide Band (UWB) Gateway (Figure 53) and the wearable sensor (Figure 54) that will be carried by the actors and will send information about their position to the UWB gateway.

Figure 53: UWB gateway

Figure 54: wearable sensor

All the above installed hardware devices are sending data to the Localization Manager component which will be described at paragraph 7.1.6

Table 51: Information of the Status and the required input of the Localization Devices

Status
The UWB Localization Devices have been deployed at the shop floor. The UWB GW has been integrated with the LinkSmart Middleware. The UWB localization system has been tested in a first step with a non-wearable tag based on a commercial hardware platform from DecaWave ³ . In a second step the system was tested with two UWB-based wearable devices. The final UWB-based localization system is able to track two workers at the same time.
Required input
This module requires as input the coordinates at which the UWB anchor nodes were placed at the testing area as well as their identifiers.

Results of operation

The UWB Localization system will be tested with the two UWB-based wearable devices. The estimated position of workers is shown by the user interface of the Re-Adaptation toolkit. The system was integrated with the LinkSmart Catalog APIs “version 0.2.0” and distribution “version 0.2.0”..

7.1.3 Smart Sensor Network – Comfort Sensor Network

Comfort sensors are basically Wi-Fi enabled mains powered devices that are able to measure ambient temperature, humidity and light levels in order to evaluate worker comfort level in industrial environments

Table 52: Information of the Status and the required input of the depth sensor network

Status
A working prototype has been developed and deployed in CPERI. Firmware has also been developed for communication with the sensors used and with the LinkSmart middleware and the CIDEM repository.
Required input
For accurate measurement of the measured environmental parameters the sensor should be placed at a space not directly influenced by factors that could cause errors in measurements. For example exposure to direct sunlight, air conditioning or cooling fans air flows should be avoided.

³ <http://www.decawave.com/products/evk1000-evaluation-kit>

The following figure shows a comfort sensor that has been installed at the shop floor of CETH/CPERI. It has been functioning for retrieving measurement data which is posted to LinkSmart via MQTT protocol and also to the CIDEM repository via a REST api interface.

Figure 55 Comfort sensor installed at CETH/CPERI floor

Results of Operation

The comfort sensor is already installed in a preliminary setup at CETH/CPERI.

7.1.4 Smart Sensor Network - Depth Sensor Network

In this scenario, it is envisaged that the depth sensor network will be used to validate each step of the repair/ restore procedure. Depth cameras are responsible for capturing the movements of the actor during the repair/ restore procedure, detect arm (hand) gestures and combined with feedback provided by the SCADA, the success of each step will be determined. Moreover, the depth sensor network is utilized for the detection of several hazardous incidents that might occur at the shop-floor and require immediate attention. Thus, incidents such as human falls, falling items, collisions and intrusions to forbidden areas are detected and published so that the appropriate coping mechanism is triggered.

Table 53: Information of the Status and the required input of the depth sensor network

Status
The software implementation for the arm (hand) gesture recognition is already in a first draft version and simultaneously a series of actions have begun to correlate information from the SCADA while also presenting success/failure messages to the SatisFactory platform. The incident detection engine is implemented and tested in all the aforementioned incidents. Only minor improvements may occur.
Required input
Access to shop-floor and equipment topology is required for both incident detection engine and automatic surveillance of the repair/restore procedure. Furthermore, for accurate configuration and determination of successful or failed steps of a repair/restore procedure the Depth Sensor Network must have feedback from the SCADA system.

The following figure shows two of the depth sensors that have been installed at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. They have been functioning for retrieving test data in order to improve the depth sensor network's behavior and results.

Figure 56 Depth camera installed at CERTH/CPERI floor

Results of Operation

The implementation of the Depth Sensor Network is part of T3.3 which is due M30. However, given the integration effort that will be required among the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager, the Multiple-Media Manager and the Localization Manager, a first operational version of Smart Sensor Network is already up and running. The depth cameras are already installed and have been running for over three months at CERTH/CPERI.

7.1.5 Smart Sensor Network - Thermal Sensor Network

The Thermal Sensor Network supports real-time condition monitoring of critical shop floor components (e.g. control cabinet) based on image segmentation, spatio-temporal image analysis (analysis of aggregated energy images) and template matching for abnormal pattern detection of thermal image information, supporting the operation of the incident detection engine. The aforementioned procedure leads to reduced unscheduled down times and catastrophic failures and eventually to safer worker environments, thus increasing worker's comfort. Using a custom-made calibration pattern, the system is able to perform 3D thermal image analysis and support virtual fencing of dangerous areas, thus further improving safety within the shop floor environment.

The following figure shows two instances of a control cabinet at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. The normal function is shown at the left instance and the function with the problem is shown at the right instance. The object inside the red cycle has increased its temperature much higher than normal and the component will understand this abnormal function. A message to the involved components is going to be produced in order to examine if this situation requires an alarm or any other action.

Figure 57 Photos of a normal and an abnormal condition of a control cabinet

Table 54: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
As mentioned above a custom made calibration pattern is designed and manufactured in order to provide 3D thermal image analysis in the pilot plant. The calibration method is completed, thermal image datasets from various incidents at shop floor level have been collected while algorithms for real-time condition monitoring are implemented and validated in both offline and real-time operation. Only minor improvements may occur.
Required input
Topology information is needed as input for the Thermal Sensor Network. Thus, information stored in CIDEM is required for the Network's operation.

Results of Operation

The incident detection engine using thermal cameras has been validated both offline and in real-time field testing. Simulated incidents have been identified within the shopfloor and the algorithms have been fine-tuned based on this experimental evaluation for optimal operation in various conditions (e.g. ambient temperature fluctuations).

7.1.6 Context-Aware Manager - Localization Manager

The Localization Manager (LM) provides safety related alerts based on a geo-fencing logics service. In particular, given a set of predefined forbidden/dangerous areas, the LM detects whether workers are inside the forbidden areas on the basis on their current positions. The positions of the workers are estimated by UWB-based wearable devices and sent to LM through LinkSmart.

Table 55: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
A first version of the Localization Manager including the geo-fencing logics service has been developed and integrated with the LinkSmart middleware. The service has been tested along with

the UWB localization system.

Required input

This module requires as input localization data from UWB devices through the event manager of the middleware. In addition, a predefined set of forbidden areas at the shop floor should be defined in order to perform the geo-fencing service.

Results of operation

The LM module was successfully tested by localizing one worker. The LM generates warning alerts whether the worker is inside any forbidden area as well as when he goes outside any of them. This module is scalable, i.e., it provides the geo-fencing logics service to several tags at the same time. The system was integrated with the LinkSmart Catalog APIs “version 0.2.0” and distribution “version 0.2.0”...

Figure 58 and Figure 59 show an example of the LM functionality from a testing user interface. Figure 58 shows a worker who is moving inside a forbidden area (depicted as a green rectangle). The green color means that there are not any workers inside.

Figure 58: The worker is moving to a permitted area

Figure 59 shows an instance where a worker has entered the forbidden zone. The area has become red at the interface and a message indicating zone status is displayed. The same message, along with more details, is sent to other components of the SatisFactory platform through LinkSmart.

Figure 59: The worker has entered a forbidden area

7.1.7 Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager

The Gesture & Content Recognition Manager component has been described with details at the paragraph 5.1.6. At the BSC-6.1 will also contribute for assisting workers by demonstrating some actions or schematics regarding the shop floor area.

7.1.8 Integrated DSS - Incident Management Tools

The Incident Management Tools monitor behavior of sensors placed on reactors of a factory's system, providing primarily an on-time warning of a possible abnormal situation, and secondly a prediction of how the reactor is going to behave after at least one minute time interval, leading to a timely notification of a possible upcoming abnormal behavior which may lead to an incident. By modeling the overall system's behavior both on normal and abnormal situations through an amount of historical data, formed in time-series, real-time values will be able to be categorized either in normal state or in abnormal state according to a probability value. The system will also provide appropriate warnings and notifications for the reactor's operators through different applications and interfaces that are subscribed to the CIDEM incident topics, including the Social and Collaboration Platform.

Figure 60: Incident Notification on the Social and Collaboration Platform

Table 56: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

<p>Status</p>
<p>Extended research has been done on methods that could model behavior of factory’s systems and methods regarding incident detection and early warning notification. The most appropriate ones have been implemented and applied on a pilot plant unit at CETH/CPERI. The methods that gave interesting results are going to be integrated on the application in order to visualize behavior and make it easier to extract knowledge.</p>
<p>Required input</p>
<p>The application is reading the essential data from CIDEM. Data such as the number of systems existing in the factory, the number of units each system has and the number of sensors placed on each unit, the topology of each system/sensor, real-time and historical measurements are all provided through REST services from CIDEM.</p>

Results of Operation

The Incident Management Tools is included in the components developed in T3.3 and thus it is due M30. The application is reading the essential data from CIDEM. Data such as the number of systems existing in the factory, the number of units each system has and the number of sensors placed on each unit, the topology of each system/sensor, real-time and historical measurements are all provided through REST services from CIDEM. The version deployed at CPERI is completed and was put into real-time testing by the end of M19 and updated in M23 while optimization will continue until the final version version which is expected to be available by M29.

7.1.9 Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI

The Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices component is also being used at BSC-5.1 and BSC-5.2 and it has been analyzed at paragraph 4.1.8. The worker will wear the smart glasses and he/she will be able to receive useful information about the actions that have to be done.

7.1.10 Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon St Component

The Digital Andon Component has been described with details at the paragraph 5.1.7. At the BSC-6.1 will also contribute for assisting workers by demonstrating some actions or schematics regarding the shop floor area.

7.2 SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED

The actors at SatisFactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-6.1.

Table 57: List with the SatisFactory actors' groups that are involved at BSC-6.1

	Groups of actors
BSC 6.1	Maintenance manager
	Maintenance supervisor
	Process operator
	Process technician

7.3 STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 6.1

Business Scenario 6.1 focuses on the safety of the workers at the shop floor are. Workers feel safer in the areas that the tools operate and they are going to perform their daily actions with more confidence. The satisfaction regarding their work will increase and so will their performance. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-6.1.

Table 58: Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-6.1

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
BSC-6.1 – Recognition of accidents and path optimization for workers movement on the shop floor												
Smart Sensor Network - Dependable Network Infrastructure		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Smart Sensor Network - UWB Localization Devices		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Smart Sensor Network - Depth Sensor Network			Design		Set-up		Deployment			Operation		
Smart Sensor Network - Thermal Sensor Network			Design		Set-up		Deployment			Operation		
Context-Aware Manager - Localization Manager		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Integrated DSS - Incident Management Tools		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Multi modal & Augmented HMI's and AR devices – Glasses UI			Design		Set-up		Deployment			Operation		
Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon Component		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
GENERAL COMPONENTS												
Repository-Asset machinery, production models		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Operational platform with augmented intelligence		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools			Design			Set-up		Deployment		Operation		
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools			Design			Set-up		Deployment		Operation		
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools			Design			Set-up		Deployment		Operation		
Gamification Framework – “What's My Score” App – Gamification-based tools			Design			Set-up		Deployment		Operation		
Middleware – Device Manager		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Middleware - Core Services		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Middleware - Event Manager		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		
Event Aggregator		Design		Set-up		Deployment				Operation		

8 CONCLUSIONS - RESULTS FROM THE IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation phase of SatisFactory focuses on the deployment of the solution to the operating environment of the participating shop floors. The activities that are documented at deliverable D5.3 are related to CERTH/CPERI shop floor where the business scenarios that are derived by actor's needs and requirements are implemented. Using a formal stage-based approach the demonstration of the usage of the SatisFactory platform is targeted. Deliverable D5.3 is about the planning, the deployment and the implementation and describes the status of all the necessary components and tools and how and when they were deployed at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI.

One of the objectives of the present deliverable was to establish a common ground on which the WP5 tasks (T5.2 and T5.5), and the connected technical WPs (WP2 to WP4), will verify their development towards the demonstration to the full-scale industrial shop floors (T5.4). This work followed the business scenario driven approach, starting with the potential restrictions, any obstacles and the determination of the prerequisites for each component or group of components and identification of the participating actors. Each scenario demonstrates different aspects of the delivered tools. The implementation phase is the basis for the demonstration of SatisFactory platform. Overall at D5.3 a time schedule was prepared in order to perform the test work for all SatisFactory components/tools and prototype platform and to be tested as described. The schedule was developed in conjunction with the development operations from the WP2, WP3 and WP4 that will facilitate proper evaluation and potential reconfiguration.

The findings from the implementation at small-scale will be a reference point for the up-scaled demonstrations and will give the opportunity to the technology providing partners to handle any technical issues that will be revealed by the activities of task T5.3. Also, as a preliminary engagement of the CERTH/CPERI actors was performed, their feedback will be carefully evaluated, as the tools will be gradually delivered and will be used at the actual working environment.

ANNEX 1 – DETAILED STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES FOR INDICATIVE BSC

BSC-5.1 - Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction

Step No	Basic Steps	Pictures	Additional Info
1.	The operator or the SCADA system identifies a malfunction		Data from SCADA Current Value: TE82.F_CV Set Point: TIC82A.F_TV1 Output: TY82A.F_CV
2.	The operator declares the new job at the iDSS		
3.	The technician receives the ticket for the new job and moves to the point that the system has identified		
4.	The technician opens the door of the electrical enclosure		

5.	The AR tool (e.g. tablet) displays the appropriate electrical drawings to the technician		
6.	The AR tool locates the involved fuse, screw terminals and solid state relay and magnifies on them at the schematics		
7.	If there is a hihi alarm the technician checks the solid state relay. If not go to step 14		<p>BSC51-step7 SSR_CHECK_OK</p> <p>BSC51-step7 SSR_CHECK_NOT_OK</p>
8.	After that the technician removes the appropriate fuse		
9.	The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system		

10.	The technician removes the wires of the relay and replaces it		BSC51-step10 REPLACE_SSR
11.	The technician connects back the fuse		
12.	The operator starts the auto function of the controller		
13.	The operator gives feedback whether the problem has been solved or not		
14.	If there is a lolo alarm the technician removes the appropriate fuse and checks it with the multimeter		BSC51-step14 CHECK_FUSE
15.	The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system		

16.	If the fuse is burned out, the technician replaces it		BSC51-step16 INSTALL_FUSE
17.	The technician removes the wires of the resistor from the terminals		
18.	The technician measures the resistor with the multimeter		BSC51-step18 CHECK_RESISTOR
19.	If the resistor is burned out. The AR tool indicates where the resistor is located		
20.	The technician replaces it		
21.	If not he connects back the fuse and the resistor wires		
22.	The technician takes a snapshot of the area where the equipment is placed and the AR tool displays a list with all the parts that exist at that point (from the identified assets as described at P&ID)		

23.	The technician choses the equipment that was involved along with the actions taken and the results		
24.	The AR tool sends feedback to the iDSS for the specific job (which was declared at step 2)		

BSC-5.3 - Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures

Step No	Basic Steps	Pictures
1.	Identify the MFC that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane, FT/FV-21C)	
2.	The volumetric flow rate range required at the previous experiment is 0-5000 cc/min, while the at next experiment is 0-3000 cc/min, thus another MFC, calibrated for Ethane, should be installed.	
3.	Calibrate the new MFC according to the gas (ethane) and the flow rate (0-3000 cc/min) to be used (if needed)	
4.	Uninstall the previous MFC and install the new MFC	
5.	Identify the GB that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane)	
6.	Make sure that the valve of the GB is closed	
7.	Remove the previously used GB (methane)	
8.	Install the new GB (ethane)	

9.	Update the ranges of the installed MFC in the HMI Database. The new MFC's volumetric flow rate range is 0-3000 cc/min.	
10.	Update the upper and lower boundaries of alarms in the HMI Database. Volumetric flowrate (0-3000 cc /min), pressure (0-10 barg) and temperature (0-300 °C) boundaries need to be updated.	
11.	Change the method that is used in the chromatograph so that the new outlet stream's composition can be identified. The previous method is "SYNGAS22.M" while the new one to be used is "SYNEX21.M"	
12.	After everything (MFC & GB) have been installed in the pilot plant a pressure test needs to be performed in order to check for possible leaks before operating the unit.	
13.	In order to perform a pressure loss test Valves HV-81 (or HV-80) and 6HV-81 needs to be (manually) closed.	
14.	Subsequently nitrogen is introduced into the system by setting the appropriate MFC's (FC-21C) volumetric flow rate at 200 cc/min.	
15.	When the pressure at PI-81 reaches 10 bar (depending on the reaction's conditions), the flow rate is set to 0 cc/min and Valve XV-21C is closed.	

<p>16.</p>	<p>The pressure loss test is performed overnight, pressurizing by mean of Valve XV-21C and HV-81. If loss of pressure exceeds 5% overnight, or the leaking flow exceeds 2cc/min, then check for leaks with Helium Leak Detector (HLD)</p>	
<p>17.</p>	<p>If loss of pressure exceeds 5% overnight, or the leaking flow exceeds 2cc/min, then check for leaks with Helium Leak Detector (HLD)</p>	